

Revue d'Hyménoptérologie • Journal of Hymenopterozoology

Volume 12 • 2024

ISSN 2727-3806

Éditorial

Par Benoît GESLIN, rédacteur-en-chef

Un pas après l'autre

Dans un article paru en 2021 dans la revue *Acta Oecologica*¹, nous alertions sur l'état des connaissances relatives à la distribution et à l'écologie des abeilles sauvages en France. À cette époque, la France accusait un retard considérable en la matière par rapport à ses voisins européens. Elle ne disposait ni d'une base de données centralisée, ni d'une mise à jour des listes d'espèces (les dernières datant des travaux de RASMONT *et al.*, 1995² puis 2007³), et encore moins d'une liste rouge dédiée aux abeilles de France. En seulement trois ans, un effort considérable a été déployé par la communauté des mellittologues, français ou européens, pour rattraper ce retard. À l'heure où j'écris ces lignes, l'Observatoire des Abeilles, grâce à l'engagement de toutes et tous, a rassemblé plus de 600 000 données d'occurrences sur les abeilles de France. Une liste rouge est également en cours d'élaboration et devrait voir le jour à l'horizon 2026. Quant à la mise à jour de la liste des abeilles de France, elle devrait paraître dans nos colonnes dans les semaines à venir.

Certes, nous aurions sans doute pu accomplir davantage ou aller plus vite. Cependant, malgré un renouveau certain ces dernières années parmi les taxonomistes et les universitaires, nos effectifs restent bien insuffisants pour achever toutes les tâches nécessaires. Ce numéro d'*Osmia*, légèrement plus court que ceux des années précédentes, témoigne des défis auxquels nous faisons face et de notre difficulté à tout mener de front.

Néanmoins, à notre mesure, nous sommes fiers de continuer notre mission d'amélioration des connaissances autour des Hyménoptères sauvages. Ainsi, dans ce numéro, vous aurez le plaisir de découvrir les premières observations d'*Eucera breviceps* pour la France et l'Italie ainsi que la description d'une nouvelle espèce (*Lasioglossum inexpectatum*) présente en Corse et en Sardaigne. Parmi d'autres contributions, nous sommes également heureux de publier la première liste commentée des abeilles de la région Centre-Val de Loire.

Pour conclure cet éditorial, je tiens à remercier chaleureusement Tanguy JEAN, l'un des piliers d'*Osmia* depuis 2016, qui quittera progressivement le comité éditorial en 2025 pour relever de nouveaux défis. Merci, Tanguy, pour ton dévouement et ton travail exceptionnel. De notre côté, nous continuerons à faire de notre mieux pour publier des articles toujours plus enrichissants et à faire vivre l'entomologie.

GESLIN, B. (2024). Editorial: One step at the time. *Osmia*, 12: ii. <https://doi.org/10.47446/OSMIA12.edito>

Published (online) 31 December 2024
<https://zoobank.org/30580DC5-45FE-4DE4-817D-1F4388BEE1C8>

¹ SCHATZ, B., M. DROSSART, M. HENRY, B. GESLIN, F. ALLIER, C. SAVAJOL, M. GÉRARD & D. MICHEZ (2021). Pollinator conservation in the context of global changes with a focus on France and Belgium. *Acta Oecologica*, 112: 103765. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actao.2021.103765>

² RASMONT, P., A. W. EBMER, J. BANASZAK & G. VAN DER ZANDEN (1995). Hymenoptera Apoidea Gallica. Liste taxonomique des abeilles de France, de Belgique, de Suisse et du Grand-Duché de Luxembourg. *Bulletin de la Société entomologique de France*, 100(special issue): 1–98. http://www.atlashymenoptera.net/biblio/00500/Rasmont_et_al_1995_Apoidea_Gallia.pdf [accessed 20 May 2024]

Editorial

By Benoît GESLIN, editor-in-chief

One step at the time

In a 2021 article published in *Acta Oecologica*¹, we highlighted the critical gap in knowledge regarding the distribution and ecology of wild bees in France. At that time, France lagged significantly behind its European counterparts, lacking a centralized database, updated species lists (the most recent being those of RASMONT *et al.*, 1995² and 2007³), and, most notably, a red list dedicated to its bee fauna.

Over the past three years, a concerted effort by the community of mellittologists, across France and Europe, has been undertaken to bridge this gap. As of today, the Bee Observatory, supported by the collective contributions of researchers and practitioners, has compiled over 600,000 occurrence records for wild bees in France. Additionally, work on a national Red List is well underway, with its publication anticipated by 2026. The updated checklist of French bees is also nearing completion and is expected to appear in these pages in the coming weeks.

Of course, we could probably have achieved more or moved faster. However, despite a noticeable renewal in recent years of both taxonomists and academics, our workforce remains insufficient to carry out all the necessary tasks. This issue of *Osmia*, slightly shorter than previous years, reflects the challenges we face and the difficulty of managing everything at the same time.

Nevertheless, we are proud, within our means, to continue our primary mission of improving knowledge about wild Hymenoptera. In this issue, you will have the pleasure of discovering the first records of *Eucera breviceps* in France and Italy, as well as the description of a new species, *Lasioglossum inexpectatum*, found in Corsica and Sardinia. Among other contributions, we are also delighted to publish the first annotated list of bees from the Centre-Val de Loire region.

To conclude this editorial, I would like to express my sincere gratitude to Tanguy JEAN, one of the main actors of *Osmia* since 2016, who will gradually leave the editorial team in 2025 to take on new challenges. Thank you, Tanguy, for your dedication and outstanding work. On our end, we will remain committed to maintain the high standards of *Osmia* and to publish articles that advance and contribute to the broader field of entomology.

Cover • Couverture

Hylaeus variegatus ♂

June • juin 2014

Pointe des Chats, Groix, Morbihan, France

Photo D. DENOUD

³ RASMONT, P., D. GENOUD, S. GADOUM, M. AUBERT, É. DUFRENE, G. LE GOFF, G. MAHÉ, D. MICHEZ & A. PAULY (2017). *Hymenoptera Apoidea Gallica: liste des abeilles sauvages de Belgique, France, Luxembourg et Suisse*. Laboratoire de zoologie, Université de Mons (Belgium), 15 pp. http://www.atlashymenoptera.net/biblio/01500/414_Rasmont_et_al_2017_Hymenoptera_Apoidea_Gallica_2017_02_16.pdf [accessed 20 May 2024]

ARTICLE

Megachile parietina (GEOFFROY, 1785), a new addition to the bee fauna of the Maltese Islands (Hymenoptera: Apoidea: Megachilidae)

Thomas CASSAR¹

CASSAR, T. (2024). *Megachile parietina* (GEOFFROY, 1785), a new addition to the bee fauna of the Maltese Islands (Hymenoptera: Apoidea: Megachilidae). *Osmia*, 12: 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.47446/OSMIA12.1>

Abstract

Megachile parietina (GEOFFROY, 1785), the black mud bee, is recorded from the Maltese Islands for the first time on the basis of two adult nesting females and four nests from Pembroke (north-east of Malta). This addition to the Maltese entomofauna brings the number of bees known from the archipelago to 106. The possibility that this species could be a suitable pollinator of the endemic orchid *Ophrys melitensis* (SALK.) DEVILLERS-TERSCHUREN & DEVILLERS, 1994 is discussed, and further investigation is encouraged.

Keywords | *Chalicodoma* • pollinators • new record • orchid • Mediterranean basin

***Megachile parietina* (GEOFFROY, 1785), un nouvel ajout à la faune des abeilles des îles maltaises (Hymenoptera : Apoidea : Megachilidae)**

Résumé

Megachile parietina (GEOFFROY, 1785) est signalée pour la première fois dans les îles maltaises sur la base de deux femelles adultes nicheuses et de quatre nids à Pembroke (nord-est de Malte). Cet ajout à l'entomofaune maltaise porte à 106 le nombre d'abeilles connues de l'archipel. La possibilité que cette espèce puisse être un pollinisateur de l'orchidée endémique *Ophrys melitensis* (SALK.) DEVILLERS-TERSCHUREN & DEVILLERS, 1994 est discutée et une enquête plus approfondie est encouragée.

Mots-clefs | *Chalicodoma* • pollinisateurs • nouveau signalement • orchidée • Bassin méditerranéen

Reçu • Received | 18 July 2023 || **Accepté** • Accepted | 06 February 2024 || **Publié (en ligne)** • Published (online) | 10 February 2024
Reviewers | Y. BRUGEROLLES • M. ZAKARDJIAN || <https://zoobank.org/BD73C2C6-C9E7-40EE-89AD-CB4CB09D7090>

INTRODUCTION

The bees of the Maltese Islands have not been extensively studied, but the last decade has seen a renewed interest in the Maltese apoidean fauna; so far, 105 species from five families have been recorded in the archipelago, in addition to three dubious records (ALFKEN, 1929; VALLETTA, 1971, 1979; SCHEMBRI, 1982; BALZAN *et al.*, 2016, 2017, 2023; CASSAR & MIFSUD, 2020a). The known bee fauna of the Maltese archipelago is composed largely of species with widespread distributions throughout the Palearctic, with nearly all species also found elsewhere in South Europe, and the bee faunas of Sicily and Malta share a strong resemblance

(BALZAN *et al.*, 2016). The bee fauna of the Maltese archipelago is still not wholly known, and ongoing studies continue to reveal new discoveries. This article reports one such discovery of another widely-distributed Palearctic species – the first record of the black mud bee *Megachile parietina* (GEOFFROY, 1785). The discovery of this species in the Maltese Islands is not only of interest from an entomological perspective as it is possible that *M. parietina* may act as a pollinator for the scarce endemic orchid *Ophrys melitensis*.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

While filming orchids in Pembroke, north-east Malta, the author encountered a dark bee, around 15 millimeters in

length, constructing a pedotrophic nest cell attached to exposed coralline limestone. After further investigation, an

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additional female and three completed nests were found, and the bee was identified to belong to the taxon *Megachile parietina* (GEOFFROY, 1785) based on morphological traits described in PRAZ (2017). The areas of Pembroke in which the bees were collected and observed are part of an expanse of coastal karstic garigue, characterized by exposed, weathered coralline limestone with shallow depressions (kamenitzas), terra-rossa soils, low-growing aromatic shrubs,

and geophytes. The area is subject to anthropic activities; a large reverse-osmosis plant occurs nearby; a metal walkway cuts across the garigue; and some parts nearer to the shore are subjected to the activities of the Armed Forces of Malta. In more disturbed areas of the garigue, such as the margins close to walkways, footpaths and roads, the vegetation becomes increasingly characterized by therophytes and ruderal species.

NEW RECORD

Megachile (Chalicodoma) parietina (GEOFFROY, 1785)

Material examined

Malta. 1 ♂ (TC), Pembroke, 3.IV.2023, T. CASSAR leg.; 1 ♀, Pembroke, 8.IV.2023, T. CASSAR obs.

Notes

This species is a widely distributed one, occurring in West, East (including North Caucasus and Crimea) and South Europe, much of the Middle East, Central Asia and North Africa (FATERYGA *et al.*, 2018). *Megachile parietina* collects particles of soil and binds them with a labial secretion, constructing dome-shaped nests containing multiple cylindrical cells provisioned with pollen and nectar – favouring that of Fabaceae – all sealed with mud. The nests are usually built directly on exposed rock surfaces and walls but may occasionally be constructed around twigs and branches (REBMANN, 1969; WESTRICH, 1989; MÜLLER *et al.*, 1997; VEREECKEN *et al.*, 2010; GOGALA, 2014). In many respects, the nesting biology of *M. parietina* closely matches that of its consubgenus *Megachile sicula* (ROSSI, 1792) which is common and widespread in the Maltese Islands and occurs in the karstic coastal garigue of Pembroke (figure 1), where the specimens of *M. parietina* were found.

Figure 1. General habitat in which bees were encountered constructing nests – coastal karstic garigue with rocky exposed ground, shallow soil and low-lying aromatic shrubs. Photo T. CASSAR.

Two females were encountered in Pembroke. The first, which was collected by the author (figure 2), had recently begun constructing a pedotrophic nest in a shallow depression in exposed limestone, with one cell complete and the wall of another still being constructed. The second was encountered 300 m away (coordinates: 35°55'59.1" N, 14°28'52.0" E) in the very final stages of completing an entire nest (also on exposed coralline limestone) by sealing the cells, and another two freshly completed nests were found less than one m from this activity (figure 3). This latter female was filmed by the author but not collected.

Figure 2. *Megachile (Chalicodoma) parietina* (Geoffroy, 1785), ♀, from Pembroke, Malta Front view and lateral view. Photo T. CASSAR.

Because of this species' widespread distribution in the Mediterranean, *M. parietina* can be assumed to be a native species which has simply remained undetected during previous samplings of Maltese Apoidea. However, the species is a large and distinctive one, having a robust build, conspicuous black colouration, wholly infuscated wings and an upper bound of length closely approaching two centimetres. Thus, it would seem unlikely to avoid detection

Figure 3. Completed nest of *M. parietina* from Pembroke, Malta.
Photo T. CASSAR.

unless particularly rare, and the possibility that it may represent an introduced species for Malta is not entirely excluded. Certainly, other hymenopterans are known to have entered the Maltese Islands (and subsequently established themselves) through the accidental transport of pedotrophic nests attached to goods, marine vessels and so on (CASSAR & MIFSUD, 2020b). However, it seems unlikely

that *M. parietina* would construct its nest on a marine vessel itself, as it tends to build its nests directly on exposed rock and, less frequently, branches and twigs (REBMANN, 1969; VERECKEN *et al.*, 2010). The most likely explanation in the view of the author, therefore, is that the bee represents a native species which has remained undetected due to (i) its rarity, (ii) the lack of previous sampling for bees carried out in a particular area to which it may be localized (Pembroke), and/or (iii) the lack of previous sampling for bees carried out during the flight period of this species.

It is interesting to note that in both areas in which the author observed females of *M. parietina* constructing nests, small populations of the endemic and scarce orchid *Ophrys melitensis* (SALK.) DEVILLERS-TERSCH. & DEVILLERS (figure 4) were in flower. So far, the only known pollinator of this plant is the male of *Megachile (Chalicodoma) sicula*, with pollinia being attached to the male's frons upon pseudocopulation (SALKOWSKI, 2000). The possibility that males of *M. parietina* could also serve well as pollinators of this orchid is not entirely excluded; *M. sicula* and *M. parietina* are closely related species (PRAZ, 2017). The author remained at the site were the second *M. parietina* female was completing its nest and closely observed the *Ophrys melitensis* flowering there for four hours (10:00 – 14:00) a day for three days (8–10 April 2023), but no males of *M. parietina* were seen pseudocopulating with *O. melitensis*. Nevertheless, the author encourages further investigation to ascertain whether this bee may be an additional pollinator of the scarce and endemic taxon *O. melitensis*.

Figure 4. One of multiple *Ophrys melitensis* plants growing about one metre from nesting *M. parietina*.
Photo T. CASSAR.

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ARTICLE

First observations of *Eucera (Cubitalia) breviceps* (FRIESE, 1911) in Italy and France, with updated information on the distribution and ecology of the species (Hymenoptera: Anthophila: Apidae)

Matthieu AUBERT¹

AUBERT, M., M. BONIFACINO, D. GENOUD, V. LECLERCQ & B. SCHATZ (2024). First observations of *Eucera (Cubitalia) breviceps* (FRIESE, 1911) in Italy and France, with updated information on the distribution and ecology of the species (Hymenoptera: Anthophila: Apidae). *Osmia*, **12**: 5–18. <https://doi.org/10.47446/OSMIA12.2>

Abstract

Eucera (Cubitalia) breviceps (FRIESE, 1911), hitherto only known from Turkey and Syria, was discovered in the southern part of Massif Central (France), in the "Grands Causses" area, a few years ago. It has been found to be distributed throughout it, also present in the French Alps and Italy (Valle d'Aosta, Abruzzo) as well as in southwestern Bulgaria and northern Greece. Our article presents the corresponding data, originated from field work and examination of material in collections, and gives new data for Turkey from material in the collection of the Oberösterreichisches Landesmuseum, Linz (Austria). Several ecological traits of *E. breviceps* are discussed. We especially highlight the close association between *E. breviceps* and the plant genus *Onosma* L. (Boraginaceae), based on literature and our field observations. Both their ecological requirements and their interactions illustrate the complexity of such relationships and their potential vulnerability in the context of global change. Through this remarkable example of an oligolectic interaction, we aim to promote a better consideration of pollinators, notably bees, and pollinator networks in conservation biology.

Keywords | Eucerini • Western Europe • *Onosma* L. • conservation biology • pollinators

Premières observations d'*Eucera (Cubitalia) breviceps* (FRIESE, 1911) en Italie et en France, avec des informations actualisées sur la répartition et l'écologie de l'espèce (Hymenoptera : Anthophila : Apidae)

Résumé

Eucera (Cubitalia) breviceps (FRIESE, 1911), jusqu'alors connue de Turquie et de Syrie, a été découverte dans la région des Grands Causses (Massif central) dans le sud de la France il y a quelques années. Elle s'est révélée y être assez largement distribuée, et est également présente dans les Alpes françaises, dans le Val d'Aoste et dans les Abruzzes en Italie, dans le sud-ouest de la Bulgarie et le nord de la Grèce. Notre article présente les données correspondantes provenant de nos prospections de terrain ainsi que de l'examen de spécimens en collection, et apporte de nouvelles données pour la Turquie issues de la révision de matériel au Muséum de Linz en Autriche. Nous y présentons différents éléments de l'écologie d'*E. breviceps* et, en particulier, les interactions étroites qu'elle entretient avec les plantes du genre *Onosma* L. (Boraginaceae), sur la base de la bibliographie et de nos observations *in situ*. Leurs exigences écologiques respectives et leurs interactions illustrent la complexité de telles relations et leur vulnérabilité dans le contexte des changements globaux. À travers la présentation de cet exemple remarquable d'oligolectisme, nous visons une meilleure prise en considération des pollinisateurs, notamment des abeilles, et des réseaux plantes-pollinisateurs dans le champ de la biologie de la conservation.

Mots-clefs | Eucerini • Europe de l'Ouest • *Onosma* L. • biologie de la conservation • pollinisateurs

Reçu • Received | 04 January 2023 || **Accepté • Accepted** | 07 March 2024 || **Publié (en ligne) • Published (online)** | 08 March 2024
Reviewers | R. CATANIA • D. MICHEZ || <https://zoobank.org/A625D692-9CCB-4AFD-B649-48DD45D000E8>

Supplementary material (on the website of the journal + archives in Zenodo) [<https://doi.org/10.47446/OSMIA12.2>]

Table S1. Data corresponding to material examined and mentioned in the article [saved at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10718775>]

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INTRODUCTION

The increase in human activities during the past centuries and especially since the Second World War has led to considerable changes in the biosphere and biodiversity. For most taxonomic groups, global change leads to two types of impacts: firstly, the decline in species marked by a decrease in the abundance of individuals, and secondly the simplification (or homogenisation) of species assemblages and their interactions (POTTS *et al.*, 2016; FISCHER *et al.*, 2018). Thus, because of this second type of impact, species that are specialised in their ecology (food preference, habitat preference, short phenology, *etc.*) are more threatened than generalist species, as the latter are more flexible in their ecological requirements and can adapt more easily to environmental variations. Wild bees are not exempted from these two components of biodiversity decline (DROSSART & GÉRARD, 2020; ZATTARA & AIZEN, 2021). While some species are exhibiting stable distributions or are even favoured by global changes, depending on their biology and ecological preferences in specific contexts (GHISBAIN *et al.*, 2021), a lot of species that are ecologically specialised are in decline (BIESMEIJER *et al.*, 2006; BOMMARCO *et al.*, 2012). Indeed, an oligolectic bee species must cope with global changes depending on its own ecology, phenology, and distribution (DUCHENNE *et al.*, 2020) but also in regard to the ecology of the few plants on which it is specialised (flowering phenology, floral attractants, general morphology) and their distribution (HUTCHINGS *et al.*, 2018). Moreover, it must deal with the several interaction dimensions with the host plants (phenological synchronisation, morphological matching, chemical and visual mediation) (GÉRARD *et al.*, 2020). This is why oligolectic bees can be considered as sentinels of the conservation status of the functional diversity of pollinator communities. Given the need to update the conservation status of oligolectic bees in general, and particularly in Southern Europe, this study presents an overview of the information known about one remarkable bee species, *Eucera (Cubitalia) breviceps* FRIESE, 1911, specialised on some species of the genus *Onosma* (Boraginaceae). We aimed to highlight the importance of this association with considerations of conservation.

General information on *Cubitalia* bees

Cubitalia FRIESE, 1911 represents a small palearctic group of longhorn bees in the tribe Eucerini (family Apidae) that have two submarginal cells in the forewing (MICHENER, 2007). It was established and differentiated as a subgenus of *Eucera*, a genus which comprises the rest of the species with two submarginal cells, with *E. breviceps* designated as the type

species (FRIESE, 1911). The taxonomic status of *Cubitalia* has been unstable as that of the genus *Eucera* in general. It has been considered either as a subgenus of *Eucera* (RISCH, 1999) or as a distinct genus (TKALCŮ, 1984; PESENKO & SITDIKOV, 1988, 1990; SITDIKOV & PESENKO, 1988; MICHENER, 2007), and was further divided into an additional two subgenera: *Pseudeucera* TKALCŮ, 1978 and *Opacula* PESENKO & SITDIKOV, 1988. The latter authors even raised these taxa to a generic rank. Based on molecular and morphological phylogenetic analyses, DORCHIN *et al.*, (2018) proposed to include all members of *Cubitalia* among other taxa in a large genus *Eucera*.

To the present knowledge the subgenus *Cubitalia* (sensu RISCH) includes eight species (TKALCŮ, 1984; RISCH, 1999; ENGEL, 2006), which are distributed in southwestern Asia (Israel, Jordan, Syria, Turkey, Georgia, Russian Caucasus, Iran), with *Eucera (Cubitalia) donatica* (SITDIKOV, 1988 in PESENKO & SITDIKOV, 1988) (= *Cubitalia (Opacula) donatica*) distributed in Central Asia (Uzbekistan) (SITDIKOV & PESENKO, 1990). Two species are known to be present in South-Eastern Europe: *Eucera (Cubitalia) morio* FRIESE, 1922, and *Eucera (Cubitalia) parvicornis* (MOCSÁRY, 1878) (= *Cubitalia (Pseudeucera) parvicornis*) (KUHLMANN *et al.*, 2015).

Recent lists of the Western European fauna of eucerine bees, particularly from France (RASMONT *et al.*, 2017; GARGOMINY *et al.*, 2021) and Italy (PAGLIANO, 1995; STOCH *et al.*, 2003; COMBA, 2019) indicate the presence of *Eucera parvicornis* in Italy (but not in France) and delineate the western boundary of distribution of the subgenus *Cubitalia* in Italy. For example, GRANDI (1931) reported this species in Emilia-Romagna, and COMBA (2019) in Lazio where he caught a single male, whose identity was confirmed by Borek TKALCŮ (M. CORNALBA, *pers. comm.*).

Available observations suggest that females of the subgenus *Cubitalia* exclusively collect pollen from flowers in the plant family Boraginaceae (RISCH, 1999). MÜLLER (1995) contributed details of the pollen collection of *Eucera parvicornis*, showing that this species is specialised in the Boraginaceae and, above all, in *Anchusa* L., strongly preferred genus. DUKAS & DAFNI (1990) reported that *Eucera (Cubitalia) boyadjiani* VACHAL, 1907 (as *C. boyadjiani*) collected the pollen of different species of the genus *Onosma* in Israel. Finally, based on fieldwork conducted in Greece, TEPPNER (1995) indicated that a species of *Cubitalia* was oligolectic to the genus *Onosma*.

CUBITALIA NEW TO WESTERN EUROPE: HISTORY OF DISCOVERY IN FRANCE AND IN ITALY AND TAXONOMIC CLARIFICATIONS

In the end of June 2010, one of us (MA) participated in fieldwork at the southern department of Lozère, France. It took place specifically on Causse Méjean, a limestone plateau which altitude ranges from 800 m to nearly 1250 m (FONDERFLICK *et al.*, 2010), in an area covered by dry calcareous substeppic grasslands. On this occasion were caught two eucerine bee individuals, one female and one

male while *in copula*. They turned out to correspond to representatives of a *Cubitalia* species, which was neither *E. parvicornis* nor *E. morio*.

This discovery was all the most surprising considering the bee size and robustness (for more details on their identification and habits see taxonomic clarifications in

Figure 1. *Eucera breviceps* habitat on Causse Méjean (Lozère, France, 13 June 2016), with large *Onosma tricosperma* subsp. *fastigiata* stand. Photo Matthieu AUBERT.

Table I. Locations and years of capture of *Eucera breviceps* in Western Europe

All studied specimen data are presented in online supplementary material (table S1). Administrative units refer to departments in France and provinces in Italy. Abbreviated names of collectors refer to the authors.

Administrative entities		Natural regions	Year(s) of collection	Altitude (m)	Collector(s)
Regions (Country)	Administrative units				
Occitanie (France)	Aveyron	Causse du Larzac	2020	810	MA
	Gard	Causse Noir	2014, 2018, 2021	910–940	MA, DG
		Causse de Blandas	2016, 2017, 2018	700	BS, Marie ZÉLAZNY, Natasha DE MANINCOR
	Hérault	Causse du Larzac	2021	675	BS
	Lozère	Causse Méjean	2010, 2013, 2016, 2018, 2021, 2022	920	MA, DG, BS, Cédric MROCZKO, Rémi RUDELLE
		Causse de Sauveterre	2021	950	DG
PACA (France)	Hautes-Alpes	Serranais-Rosannais	2022	1075	VL
Abruzzo (Italy)	Pescara	Gran Sasso foothills	2022	550	MB
Valle d'Aosta (Italy)	Aosta	Valley base, southern slopes	1977	700–900	Erwin STEINMANN
			2005	650	Gilles CARON

box A). We hypothesized that the species is either very rare, localized, or both, in France. In any case, this finding marked the beginning of further research during the following years. This initially took place in the same area and type of habitat, and in the same season that coincided with the assumed flight period of the species. The supposedly restricted diet of the species also helped to determine following fieldwork. It was assumed that this *Cubitalia* should be associated with Boraginaceae as in other *Cubitalia* species. To improve the chances to find it again, we tried to recognize precisely which plants it could use for pollen collection in such a habitat. We

thought some stenoecious plant would be a good candidate.

One member of the genus *Onosma* caught our attention: *O. tricosperma* subsp. *fastigiata* (BRAUN-BLANQ.) G. LÓPEZ, 1994, which is associated with dry calcareous grassland. It is indeed well represented in open landscapes of Causse Méjean and blooms from May to July (BERNARD 2009; TISON et al., 2014). Moreover, the centre of diversity of *Onosma* is in eastern Turkey and adjacent countries (BINZET et al., 2018) as is the case for the *Cubitalia* bees.

Box A. Brief description of *Eucera breviceps* FRIESE, 1911**Size**

- **Female** around 17–18 mm long.
- **Male** around 18–19 mm long.

Important characters

- Both sexes have a relatively long tongue (galea length is a little less than 0.4-time body length) and a cubical head.
- The labrum is longer than it is wide, ending in a triangle (it is nearly rhomboidal in males).
- As in other *Cubitalia* representatives (MICHENER, 2007; AUBERT, 2020), the first recurrent vein insertion on the back of second submarginal cell is closer to the second submarginal cross-vein than in other palearctic eucerines with two submarginal cells.

Pilosity

- Pilosity is well developed.
- It is particularly dense and long on the head, especially behind the compound eyes, on the genae, labrum and mandibles, as well as on the first femora and thorax sides and underside. In females, it forms a kind of brush on the labrum.
- The pilosity is white on the ventral part of the body, except on the central area of the last sternites where it is black.
- Dorsal part, from the head to the second tergite, is covered with orange pilosity in fresh specimens, set apart on female occiput and forehead where it is black (and even sometimes on the disc of tergite 1).
- Leg pilosity is more or less orange too, mainly on their outer surfaces. Scopa is brownish orange.

About males

- Males bear elongated antennas, but less long than in other west-European eucerines (they only reach the back of the thorax, whereas they are as long as body length, reaching abdomen tip in *Eucera nigrescens* PÉREZ, 1879 for example).
- Their mandibles are particularly long, approximately reaching clypeus width. The labrum and the apical two-thirds of clypeus are yellow-coloured. Second and third pairs of metatarsi are modified.

Differences between *E. breviceps* and *E. tristis*

- Diagnostic characters given by TKALCÚ (1984) to distinguish *E. breviceps* from *E. tristis*, its closest relative, have appeared to us hard to use. Females differ by their vestiture, which is entirely dark in *E. tristis*. Apart from that, differences are not obvious.
- Our difficulties also concern the males. Indeed, the variability we have noticed notably on some genitalia and last sternites details (apex of gonostyli and seventh sternite shapes for example) among the examined series of *E. breviceps* make the proposed criteria difficult to consider. A taxonomic revision concerning the status of these two taxa would certainly be relevant.

Illustrations

- Female and male are illustrated respectively in the figures a–b (+ figure 7), and figures c–d.
- Genitalia and last sternites of the latter are illustrated by TKALCÚ (1984).

Figure a. *Eucera breviceps* female seen in profile on *Onosma tricosperma* subsp. *fastigiata* flower (Lozère, France, 13 June 2016). Photo Matthieu AUBERT.

Figure b. *Eucera breviceps* female seen from the back on *Onosma tricosperma* subsp. *fastigiata* (Lozère, France, 13 June 2016). Photo Matthieu AUBERT.

Figure c. *Eucera breviceps* male seen in 3/4 view (Lozère, France, 13 June 2016). Photo Matthieu AUBERT.

Figure d. *Eucera breviceps* male held between the fingers, in front view (Lozère, France, 13 June 2016). Photo Matthieu AUBERT.

French overall distribution

Following the first record, the *Cubitalia* species was indeed regularly found on the southern part of Massif Central. Data was taken on Causse Méjean and again for several comparable limestone plateaus: Causse Noir, Causse de Blandas, Causse du Larzac and Causse de Sauveterre (table I). The species was systematically found on dry grasslands hosting *Onosma* populations, from around 700 m (Causse du Larzac and Causse de Blandas) to 1045 m (Causse de Sauveterre) of altitude (figures 1–2).

In addition, during the June 6th, 2022, additional surveys were performed in the French southern Alps. This is because *Eucera breviceps* was suspected to occur there considering the presence of suitable habitats with the host plant *O. tricosperma* subsp. *fastigiata*, and presence of the species in the Italian Alps (following part). It was indeed found by VL in the Serranais-Rosannais area, southwest of Gap (Hautes-Alpes department). Two females were collected on two closed dry grasslands with *O. tricosperma* ssp. *fastigiata*, at an altitude of around 1000 m to 1100 m (figure 3).

Presence in Italy

Conversations with Christophe PRAZ (Neuchâtel, Switzerland) and Andreas MÜLLER (Zürich, Switzerland) about the discovery of a *Cubitalia* species in France highlighted two specimens caught in Aosta Valley in 1977 (Erwin STEINMANN leg.) and 2005 (Gilles CARON leg.) which are preserved in the A. MÜLLER collection. The first one is a male labelled with the following information: “11.7.77 Senin Koel. Stip. 880” (1st handwritten label, which means Koelerio-Stipetum, a plant association corresponding to a dry grassland, at 880 m high), “*Eu. curvitaris* ♂” (2nd handwritten

label) and “*Eucera breviceps* FRIESE RISCH det. 2011” (3rd label, a printed one). The second specimen is a female with one printed label indicating: “Italia: Val d’Aosta Saint-Pierre sur Château Sarre leg. G. CARRON 2.6.2005”. The collection site of the male certainly occurred above Sénin on the southern slopes. The one of the female probably corresponds to a vineyard and dry grassland mosaic that surrounds Castello Reale di Sarre (= “Château Sarre”). Both were carefully sent to MA for comparison with the *Cubitalia* individuals caught in southern France and were found to be conspecific with high likelihood.

More recently, a *Cubitalia* male of the same species was caught in the Abruzzo region, in the southern part of Gran Sasso and Monti della Laga National Park by MB. It was found on May 22nd, 2022, at just 550 meters above sea level, in a hilly area characterized by dry meadows interspersed with woods. The specimen, fairly worn, was collected in flight on a grassy slope with some plants of *Onosma echioides* (figure 4).

Species identification of the specimens from France and Italy

The first two specimens collected in France were sent by MA to Stephan RISCH for identification. They were identified as *Eucera (Cubitalia) breviceps* FRIESE, 1911 and deposited in the MA collection. Later collection events by DG contributed additional reference material that is preserved in his collection. In more recent years, some individuals were also sent to Achik DORCHIN (Mons, Belgium) who agreed with the species identity. The majority of the data presented in this article were confirmed *via* specimen examination by Stephan RISCH, MA or DG. Additional more recently collected specimens were identified only *via* photographs.

Figure 2. *Eucera breviceps* habitat on Causse du Larzac (Aveyron, France), 20 June 2020. Photo Matthieu AUBERT.

Figure 3. *Eucera breviceps* habitat in southern Alps (Hautes-Alpes, France). 6 June 2022. Photo Vincent LECLERCQ.

Figure 4. *Eucera breviceps* habitat in Abruzzo (Pescara, Italy). 22 May 2022. Photo: Marco BONIFACINO.

Examination of Italian specimens agreed with the species identification of the French specimens. Comparison between French and Italian specimens showed that morphological and anatomical variations can be greater between specimens coming from the same region in France than between specimens that originated in each of the countries. These subtle differences concern cuticular punctuation particularly in females, and the structure of the 7th and 8th sternites as well as genitalia of males (box A). The *Cubitalia* male caught in Val d'Aosta (Sénin) was initially misidentified as *Eucera curvitaris* MOCSÁRY, 1879. Consequently, the mention of this species in Aosta (STEINMANN, 2002) is erroneous. This east-European and east-Mediterranean *Hetereucera* (*sensu* TKALCŮ, 1978) is currently considered absent from Italy, as STEINMANN's article is the only evidence of the species occurrence there that is cited in COMBA's checklist (2019).

Eucera breviceps overall distribution

FRIESE described *E. breviceps* on the basis of four syntypes, two females and two males. In the framework of a *Cubitalia sensu stricto* revision (including *E. boyadjani*, *E. breviceps*, *E. morio* and *E. tristis* MORAWITZ, 1876), TKALCŮ (1984) examined one male and one female only, which were deposited in Museum für Naturkunde, Berlin. He presumed the two other male and female to be lost. TKALCŮ identified only the male as *Cubitalia* and the female as belonging to another species, and erroneously paired with the male. According to him, it belonged to the subgenus *Hetereucera* (this female was described later and referred to as the holotype of *Eucera maxima* (TKALCŮ, 1987)).

Among the syntypes, the two males and the remaining female – which actually correspond to *E. maxima* – come from the eastern Taurus range in south-central Turkey ("Güleck im Taurus cilic."). The female that is presumably lost came from Syria, potentially from a north-western part of the country as indicated by ENGEL (2006) (it is probable that this specimen was later associated with *E. maxima* as well).

TKALCŮ (1984) provided a map in which he indicated the provenance of the Turkish syntypes (but not that of the Syrian syntype). He illustrated supplementary data from Hatay province, adjacent to Syria (in the Amanus range) which corresponds to a specimen that was deposited in the Oberösterreichisches Landesmuseum (OÖLM), Linz (Austria). In the same article, TKALCŮ mentioned another individual caught in Sertavul (Mersin province), which lies in Central Taurus range in southern Turkey.

A visit at OÖLM in 2019 permitted MA to compile data that concern *E. breviceps* in Turkey from several other provinces: Hakkari and Siirt in south-eastern Turkey (Turkish Kurdistan), the former location including the Cilo-Sat range, on the border of Iran and Iraq, Kars in eastern Turkey, adjacent to Armenia, Cankiri and Ankara in the central northern part of Turkey, and Aydin in the southwestern part of the country, along the Mediterranean Sea. Thus, the distribution of *E. breviceps* in Turkey encompasses a large part of the country, from East to West. Moreover, two *E. breviceps* males taken from southwestern Bulgaria were found at OÖLM, in Maximilian SCHWARZ collection. They were collected there by Miroslaw KOCOUREK and were both

Figure 5. *Eucera breviceps* distribution maps with a focus on South-eastern France and Northern Italy (map generated with QGIS).

labelled as follows: “Sandanski 06/1969” and “*Eucera cf. tristis* MORAWITZ, 1876”.

Finally, TEPPNER (1995) reported field observations of visitors of *Onosma*. His studies were performed in northern Greece, notably the Falakron area. One of them concerns a *Cubitalia* species visiting *Onosma stajanoffi* (TURRIL) TEPPNER. A female specimen was collected and identified as *Eucera morio* FRIESE (referred to as *Cubitalia morio* (FRIESE)). The article comprises some black and white pictures of limited resolution, but the appearance of the specimen does not seem to us to match the species concept of *E. morio* as we understand it. Indeed, as indicated in TKALCÚ’s revision (1984), *E. morio* has darkened wings and nearly entirely dark pilosity, while the pilosity of the Falakron female, especially on the thorax, is light. We therefore inquired with H. TEPPNER, who has kindly provided us with higher resolution colour photographs of the same specimen, which confirm it doesn’t

match with *E. morio*. In addition to the coloration, an important diagnostic feature of the first tergite allows to exclude this species. We couldn’t examine the Falakron specimen under the dissecting microscope, but we are convinced that it belongs to *E. breviceps*. It differs merely in the colour of the pilosity of the first and second tergites. While the tergal hair pilosity is commonly light as that of the thorax, it is mostly darker in the specimen studied by TEPPNER, with some intermixed pale hairs limited to the sides of first tergite. We think that this specimen only presents a morphological variation of *E. breviceps*, that may be typical to higher elevations as the specimen in question was caught at an altitude of 1400 m.

All the mentioned data are mapped in the figure 5. All studied specimen data are presented in table S1 (online supplementary materials).

ELEMENTS OF ECOLOGY

Flight period, relative abundance and rareness

E. breviceps is clearly univoltine: its flight period is probably short, no longer than three or four weeks for the majority of individuals in a given generation. In Italy and France, it was contacted from last decade of May to the first decade of July, with a peak in June (figure 6).

Concerning abundance, still considering only Italy and France, 23 of the 30 occurrences (*i.e.* collection or observation of the species at one place and one date, that is one fieldwork) correspond to only 1 specimen. Two

occurrences correspond to 2 specimens, four occurrences correspond to 3 or 4 specimens and one occurrence corresponds at least to 8 specimens (males and females).

Besides, as indicated earlier, several surveys conducted in France led to no contacts. Indeed, between 2013 and 2019, especially on the Larzac plateau (La Couvertoirade, Saint-Maurice-Navacelle, Saint-Michel), as well as in 2022 on the northwest border of Var department (in the vicinity of Trigance village), some focused field research in suitable habitats did not lead to *E. breviceps* collection or observation. In most cases, it was noticed that *Onosma*

Figure 6. Number of females and males collected or observed in France and Italy per 5-day periods between mid-May to mid-July from 1977 to 2022.

flowering peak was over, though some flowers remained. Moreover, on most occasions (except near Trigance), no high *Onosma* densities but only sparse individual plants were found (often about ten or a little more, distributed over hundreds to thousands of square metres, as it could be observed). Some *Cubitalia* specimens were found under comparable flower densities, but only by applying a rather important time of survey (for example it took around one hour for each female caught in the Hautes-Alpes department in France).

The absence of observations does not mean systematically the absence of bees in these studied areas, but either an insufficient study design in regard to the bee density or an inappropriate study date. However, it is likely that there is a threshold in terms of the number and density of *Onosma* that allows the detection and above all the sufficient feeding of *E. breviceps*.

Other ecological factors may explain the absence of the species. Indeed, the altitudinal distribution of *E. breviceps* appears to be relatively restricted in France and Italy (table 1), though large populations of *Onosma* are also present at high altitudes in southern Alps, up to 2300 m. Repeated field research undertaken by MA and colleagues at several locations around 2000 m in this area did not permit to find the species.

Since the species was only recently discovered and its apparent low abundance in most sites, it can be assumed that *E. breviceps* is indeed generally scarce. That said, research efficiency could certainly be optimized by focusing fieldwork efforts during the blooming peak of *Onosma*, and perhaps during the first part of the day when pollen may be more abundant in the flowers. As suggested earlier, that parameter could influence female behaviour and detectability.

The exceptional observations, with three, four and eight specimens observed at the same time and place may be explained by a combination of good timing (peak of flight period) and the existence of particularly suitable habitat with high *Onosma* densities. Four of the five most prolific observation events are those of the Causse Méjean and one at the Causse du Larzac in France. In each case, especially the one where at least eight specimens were observed, the density and abundance of *O. tricosperma* ssp. *fastigiata* were visibly high with dozens of plants distributed within a few hundreds of squared meters.

About close links between *E. breviceps* and *Onosma* flowers

Among the data we compiled in France, at thirteen different locations we caught or observed at least one female, that was visiting or foraging on *Onosma* flowers (as indicated previously, in some cases, the number of females observed on *Onosma* was higher). The only other visitation data concerns one female caught on *Salvia pratensis* L. (Lamiaceae).

Concerning the data gathered for Italy, the observation in the Abruzzo included an *Onosma echioides* population. The collecting period in Aosta also theoretically corresponds

with the blooming period of that genus. A. MÜLLER analysed pollen grains taken from three *Cubitalia* females, including two that originated from France, and one from Aosta (Italy). His results are the following: 100 % pear-shaped Boraginaceae pollen grains, with many typical *Onosma* grains. Nevertheless, it cannot be excluded that a certain proportion of *Echium* grains were mixed among them (MÜLLER, *pers. comm.*). We do not have direct observation information on specimens collected in Turkey, but the genus *Onosma* is abundant there and it is therefore likely that the species is associated with *Onosma* also in Turkey. It cannot be excluded however that in its eastern range of distribution, the species uses pollen from other close relatives of *Onosma*, which do not occur in its western distribution range (like *Podonosma* BOISS.).

Sonication and pollen collection

One more interesting observation on the relation between females of *E. breviceps* and *Onosma* flowers can be developed, namely floral sonication, which is observed in many bees, notably in the family Apidae, including generalists (bumblebees and some anthophorine bees) as well as specialist species.

Also known as “buzzing” or vibratory pollen collection, it is a behaviour that involves flight muscles to vibrate the flowers and extract the pollen. It produces a quite loud sound, audible from several meters. It is particularly adapted to flowers with mostly closed anthers, with only small apertures, as short slits, valves or pores (BUCHMANN, 1983; CARDINAL *et al.*, 2018; TEPPNER, 2018). In *Onosma* flowers, anthers are bent towards the style (the established term is introrse) and partly or completely connected to each other, hence forming a cone at the base inside the tubular corolla (TEPPNER, 2011). Consequently, *Onosma* pollen is enclosed and not directly accessible to bees.

Buzzing behaviour on *Onosma* flowers was already reported by DUKAS & DAFNI (1990) and TEPPNER (1995), involving several species of the plant genus and several bee species (see below). In the case of *O. tricosperma* spp. *fastigiata* and *E. breviceps* in southern France, sonication was regularly noticed in the field and even allow the bee to be heard and detected within 10–20 meters before it is seen. Its size and its pilosity appear to be arranged to optimize falling pollen capture while buzzing. The corolla size and shape of *Onosma* flowers, and the presence of an exerted style, allow *E. breviceps* to enter only its head and forelegs into the floral tube. But in doing so, it nearly entirely closes the corolla opening with the front part of the head and thorax. The effect of the ‘buzz’ action releases pollen, the majority falls onto the body of the bee, especially on its ventral side.

During examination under dissecting microscope, sparse pollen grains are visible on the pilosity of the fore region of the female: head, underneath and sides of the thorax as well as the forelegs (where the pilosity is especially dense and long). Some cuticular areas at the base of the genae and hair fringes of the first femora show some pollen deposits. In the field, between buzzing sequences, we observed the bees hanging at the tip of the corolla by the hind legs and grooming its front body parts with its forelegs. The pollen is then actively accumulated by the bee on the third tibiae, mixed with little nectar (figure 7).

Figure 7. *Eucera breviceps* female seen in profile on *Onosma tricosperma* subsp. *fastigiata* flower (Lozère, France, 13 June 2016). Photo Matthieu AUBERT.

Unfortunately, we didn't pay enough attention on the use of the glossa. As part of the bee is hidden inside the corolla for harvesting the pollen, it is difficult to directly watch this body part at this moment. We observed the glossa was deployed several times during the grooming sequence, and it is quite possible that it is used inside the corolla to collect nectar before and after sonication, as specific sequences may be required.

The eventual use of mandibles inside the corolla is not clear either. Some bumblebees were reported to « milk » the anthers to optimize the pollen extraction along with sonication (BUCHMANN, 1983). 'Milking' means here extracting pollen by pressing the anthers with their mandibles. It is a terminology used in literature while referring to poricidal anthers and it may not be relevant for anther cones. One example is known on *Onosma* flowers, which is referred to as 'leg shaking': *Osmia apicata* SMITH, 1853, oligolectic on Boraginaceae with a strong preference for *Onosma* flowers, uses its first legs to shake the anther cone to harvest pollen, without the use of flight muscles (GOGALA & SURINA, 2011). The figure 3 of their article shows a female hanging upside down under an *Onosma* corolla, that has its ventral side white with pollen. It suggests that this method could be efficient.

Yet, evolution has led to another strategy to effectively exploit the pollen of narrow corolla flowers, notably in Boraginaceae. It involves modified bristles (mostly with a hooked tip) on mouthparts or front legs, in combination with scraping behaviour (MÜLLER, 1995; SEDIVY *et al.*, 2013). But *E. breviceps* females lack such hooked bristles on their mouthparts or front legs.

We did not systematically count the number of buzzing instances per visited flower, nor measured their duration. Some of our observations suggest that females could sonicate each flower during one long period of time or, more rarely, two or three periods of times with repositioning in between. It is most probable that females adapt sonication modalities throughout the day, depending on the amount of pollen available in the flowers (BUCHMANN, 1983).

We have not talked much about males so far because we did not notice a lot about them except that they actively patrol between *Onosma* plants or patches close to the ground. Some have been observed higher up. They are less easy detected probably because they land less often. The long tongues certainly permit them, as well as females, to take up the nectar concentrated at the bottom of the flowers of *Onosma*.

Onosma* ecology in relation to *E. breviceps

Onosma flowers are present on limestone and alluvial soil and individuals are generally located and very scattered. Some populations can be relatively concentrated, on some hundred square meters, even with 20-30 ind. by 2-3 square meters, but such concentration is rare and exceptional (*pers. obs.*).

In the Occitanie region (France), *Onosma* populations are present in steppe-like grasslands typical of the limestone plateaus of the Grands Causses region. In French Alps, they are found locally in calcareous grasslands, from 850 m in Pre-Alps up to 2300 m in Haute-Ubaye Region (*pers. obs.*). In Aosta (Italy), they exist in mosaics of substeppic habitats

where it is represented by *Onosma pseudoarenaria* SCHUR where this species is the only representative of the genus (BARTOLUCCI *et al.*, 2018; MARTELLOS & NIMIS, 2022). In Turkey, the genus *Onosma* is extremely diverse (comprising dozens of species), and largely distributed (BINZET *et al.*, 2018; TEPPNER, 2011). The representatives of this plant genus are characterised by partitioned flowering, where flowers of

individuals do not flower at the same time but spread out over time (BERNARD 2009; TISON *et al.*, 2014). The downward orientation of these so-called pendulous flowers also ensures that the pollen is always well protected from rain and radiation that could alter the nutritional qualities and volume of the available pollen and nectar.

CONSERVATION ISSUES

The relation between *E. breviceps* and *Onosma* species involve several key facts about their ecology and their actual interaction. On the *E. breviceps* side, we note (1) a foraging behaviour that allows the bees to detect their host plants from a long distance, (2) a sonication behaviour allowing to optimize pollen collection, and we hypothesize (3) a relatively large flight distance (probably up to 1 km around the nest) as suggested by the large size of the individuals (GATHMANN & TSCHARNTKE, 2002). On the *Onosma* side, it is important to note (4) a floral colour and a height of the stems that allow remote detection by the bees, (5) a flowering partitioning through time, (6) large flowers directed downwards, allowing the abundant pollen to remain dry and efficient for pollination and (7) a pollination also ensured by other large bees which increase the chances of fertilization and reproduction. Finally, on the interaction side, (8) the emergence period of *E. breviceps* is synchronized with the flowering period of *Onosma* and can withstand interannual variations (this particularly can be extended to all specialist bees), and (9) an open and calcareous semi-natural habitat suitable for both species. Thus, this interaction is weakened by the low density of *Onosma* populations and the rather large distances between populations. It has been shown that increasing distances between nesting and foraging sites reduce the offspring production of bee species (ZURBUCHEN *et al.*, 2010). Because of its big size, *E. breviceps* certainly requires high amounts of *Onosma* pollen to breed new individuals, which can partly explain the relative rarity of *E. breviceps* individuals in most cases.

At least in southern France (and probably in Aosta too), the conservation of open grasslands with high *Onosma* densities in areas where both the plant and *Cubitalia* are present is certainly key to preserve the bee. This conservation directly relies on that as a whole, which can be considered at landscape scale. The grasslands and mosaics they are part of provide remarkable landscapes of high interest and are recognized as such, in the actual context. They are the results of ancestral interactions between traditional human activities and the local environment (LEPART *et al.*, 2011). In the case of French Massif Central and its southern limestone plateaus, in addition to the creation of the “Parc Naturel Régional des Grands Causses” and the “Parc National des Cévennes”, the landscape justified the inscription of the area to UNESCO world heritage list with the name “The Causses and the Cévennes, Mediterranean agro-pastoral Cultural

Landscape”. It is interesting to observe that all southern Massif Central *E. breviceps* data are included in this perimeter.

Since the nineteenth century, the landscape has become largely woodland within it, as well as in a large part of Mediterranean area, although in a heterogenous way. This reforestation is largely spontaneous due to land abandonment and may be accelerated by coniferous plantations. This increasing trend, even in areas where agropastoralism is still well developed as in « causses » context (especially in Lozère department), shows that maintaining extensive farming is not sufficient to conserve open habitats (LEPART *et al.*, 2011). The evolution of the agricultural management, in particular farm enlargements and concentrations and the resulting changes in practices (more fodder crops and less grazing), allows a more nuanced explanation. The main driver of these changes is economic and lies in the agricultural and rural policies, notably the Common Agricultural Policy (FONDERFLICK *et al.*, 2010a, 2010b). To change this trend and to combine the existence of a dynamic agriculture with the preservation of biodiversity through the maintenance of grasslands and mainly open landscapes, public grants must be conditional on the implementation of appropriate practices (FONDERFLICK *et al.*, 2010b).

Of course, global changes may have important effects on the composition of these grasslands too and could directly or indirectly affect *E. breviceps*. Many factors may influence the future of its populations, such as spring droughts which could affect both the bee, the plant and their interaction.

It would be relevant to inventory the relatively high-density populations of *Onosma* and to promote the conditions for their conservation. This attention also corresponds to the strong and growing interest in conserving ancient natural grasslands (FONDERFLICK *et al.*, 2010a, 2010b; LEPART *et al.*, 2011). Meanwhile, we encourage the monitoring of changes in use of substeppe areas, the documentation of the effects of overgrazing or the abandonment of grazing – extensive or intensive – and to provide spatial information on the reallocation of these areas towards intensive livestock farming (sheep, goat, horses and sometimes pig farming) and towards natural or anthropogenic reforestation. Areas with a regulatory status, those that are protected, could be relevant territories in this respect.

FURTHER PROSPECTS

In any event, *E. breviceps* deserves to be studied further to better know its distribution and population dynamics and to

better understand its biology and ecology. Key features like actual foraging ranges or ecological requirements would be

worth studying. It would be interesting to determine whether the distribution of this species is limited by the existence of high-density populations within the distribution of its host plant (<https://www.tela-botanica.org/bdtfx-nn-45009-repartition> and https://inpn.mnhn.fr/espece/cd_nom/138244/tab/carte) [accessed 21 April 2022]. One alternative hypothesis is that *E. breviceps* is under-sampled in other areas where this plant or a related species such as *Onosma pseudoarenaria* occurs. The answers to these questions can be provided by targeted campaigns on this remarkable bee where it has not been searched for in *Onosma* populations, as well as by assessments of *Onosma* density in sites of presence/absence of this bee.

The key factors in this close relationship could be analysed in more detail, such as the visual and olfactory mediation

linked to the interaction, but also the ecology of this plant, so as to explain the low density of these populations. The identification of threats to the reproduction of this plant, which is not very common on a national scale in France, would certainly provide information to promote its conservation.

Beyond the case of *E. breviceps* and *Onosma* species, this study also provides a conceptual framework for the study of close interactions involving other rare oligolectic bee species and host plants. This point is particularly important in the current context of the start of the establishment of the national red list of wild bees in metropolitan France. Finally, our ambition here is also to raise awareness in protected areas and conservation stakeholders of the conservation issues of these species and of these remarkable interactions.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

A special thanks goes to Andreas MÜLLER who kindly provided specimens from Aosta and who identified some pollen samples for us. The Aostan specimens were caught by the late Erwin STEINMANN and Gilles CARRON to whom we pay tribute here. A second special thanks go to Stephan RISCH and Achik DORCHIN who helped with the identification of the *Cubitalia* from Western Europe and proposed many improvements of the article. We give a great deal of thanks to all the contributors to the data compiled in the article: Natasha DE MANINCOR, Marie ZÉLAZNY (who benefited with BS from the ANR ARSENIC grant no. 14-CE02-0012), Rémi RUDELLE and Cédric MROCZKO. All of them also provided complementary information. BS and DG benefited from capture authorisation 2022-0148 and the grant n° 90555174 from the Cévennes National Park. BS benefited from the Hérault Departmental Council grant n°175578 and from the program *Pollimed* from OSU-OREME. MA and DG are very grateful to the Observatoire des Abeilles for paying for a trip to Linz to work on the extensive and essential collection of the OÖLM. We thank Esther ÖCKERMÜLLER, Martin SCHWARZ and Fritz GUSENLEITNER for the warm welcome there and their help, including the sending of pictures of *Eucera morio*. And we thank Christophe PRAZ for the organization! We also thank the following persons for their contributions. Herwig TEPPNER provided several articles and permitted us to get recent pictures of Falakron female. Bernard VAISSIÈRE kindly sent us an essential bibliographical reference. Jocelyn FONDERFLICK (Cévennes National Park) sent us several other essential articles and also mission facilities and contract for DG. Maurizio CORNALBA permitted MB's participation in the article. Amy Lily HURDISS helped us with English translation. Last but not least, we are grateful to Roberto CATANIA, Denis MICHEZ & Achik DORCHIN (once again!) for their proofreading and comments on the manuscript.

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ARTICLE

New insights into the distribution of the obscure digger wasp *Sphex optimus* F. SMITH, 1856 (Hymenoptera: Apoidea: Sphecidae)

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DÖRFEL, T. H. (2023). New insights into the distribution of the obscure digger wasp *Sphex optimus* F. SMITH, 1856 (Hymenoptera: Apoidea: Sphecidae). *Osmia*, 12: 19–22. <https://doi.org/10.47446/OSMIA12.3>

Abstract

Until now, *Sphex optimus* F. SMITH, 1856 has been known from only the holotype which had presumably been collected in Western Africa. Here, new records of a taxon from Central America with phenotypic accordance are presented. Diagnostic characters of *S. optimus* and the Neotropical species are given and the equivalence of the two taxa is being postulated.

Keywords | Insects • taxonomy • Neotropical • Central America • *iNaturalist* • citizen science

Nouvelles connaissances sur la répartition de la Guêpe fousseuse obscure *Sphex optimus* F. SMITH, 1856 (Hymenoptera: Apoidea: Sphecidae)

Résumé

Jusqu'à présent, *Sphex optimus* F. SMITH, 1856 n'était connu que par l'holotype qui avait vraisemblablement été collecté en Afrique de l'Ouest. De nouvelles données concernant un taxon d'Amérique centrale avec une concordance phénotypique sont présentés ici. Les caractères diagnostiques de *S. optimus* et de l'espèce néotropicale sont donnés et l'équivalence des deux taxons est postulée.

Mots-clefs | Insectes • taxonomie • Néotropical • Amérique centrale • *iNaturalist* • science participative

Reçu • Received | 25 December 2023 || Accepté • Accepted | 04 August 2024 || Publié (en ligne) • Published (online) | 06 August 2024
Reviewers | T. JEAN • C. SCHMID-EGGER || <https://zoobank.org/F546420C-AE36-4A60-928B-D488BBF11DC0>

INTRODUCTION

Since *Sphex optimus* was first described by British hymenopterologist Frederick SMITH in 1856, no further records of the species had ever been published (PULAWSKI, 2023), which usually indicates that a given taxon is either exceedingly rare or that its validity may in fact be dubious. In the original description, SMITH (1856) stated that the species was collected in Africa, at an unspecified location in Gambia. In 2019, while revising *Sphex* from Sub-Saharan Africa, I studied the holotype of *S. optimus* housed in the collection of the Natural History Museum in London (figure 1) as well as most other types from Afrotropical *Sphex*. In the resulting publication, I noted the lack of any additional specimens among the examined African material and the incongruity of *S. optimus* with all species groups from the continent (DÖRFEL & OHL, 2022). Based on the type's similarity to some Neotropical *Sphex* species, I expressed doubt about the

Figure 1. Holotype of *Sphex optimus* (♀).
Natural History Museum, London. Photo T. H. DÖRFEL.

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supposed locality, as mislabelings have been uncovered quite frequently in older material, and I hypothesized that

S. optimus might be synonymous to *S. melanopus* DAHLBOM, 1843.

FINDINGS

While browsing photos of Sphecidae that had been observed in Central or South America and were subsequently uploaded to the citizen science platform *iNaturalist* (www.inaturalist.org), I came across the image of a very distinct *Sphex* photographed in Costa Rica (figure 2). The sole notable identification key to include any Neotropical species of the genus only covers the fauna of Chile and Argentina (WILLINK, 1951) and does not contain any taxa that fit the specimen in question. Examination of the material in the collection of the Natural History Museum of Berlin (Naturkundemuseum Berlin) did not yield any similar specimens either. However, comparison with the photograph I had taken of the type specimen of *S. optimus* revealed striking similarities between the two individuals in all visible characteristics.

The most prominent detail is without a doubt the conspicuous color contrast regarding the patches of deep golden tomentum on head, collar and scutum versus the silvery-whitish one on the propodeal apex. The wings are slightly infuscate; metasomal segments I (excepting petiole), II and the anterior part of III are ferruginous, whereas the rest of the body is black, including the legs.

Subsequently, I was able to find six additional observations on the site that showed female specimens which also matched the appearance of *S. optimus*. The metadata from each record have been compiled below, and all localities are shown in figure 3.

Data of suspected *S. optimus*

- **Colombia.** Antioquia Department: San Jerónimo, 6°26'25.8"N, 75°42'50.1"W, 820 m, 27.XII.2018, John TSINIK. (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/21216107>)
- **Costa Rica.** Limón Province: Punta Uva, 9°38'05.0"N, 82°41'03.4"W,

Figure 2. Female *Sphex* with tettigoniid prey. Photo Jo DE PAUW (CC BY-NC 4.0), <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/20561688>, [accessed 15 December 2023], cropped.

10 m, 29.VII.2021, so-cal-bc-doc.

(<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/89136281>).

- **Costa Rica.** Puntarenas Province: Osa Peninsula, 8°24'17.8"N, 83°20'11.5"W, 35 m, 18.II.2019, Jo DE PAUW. (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/20561688>).
- **Pánama.** Chiriquí Province: Dolega, 8°36'03.0"N, 82°25'21.9"W, 346 m, 10.XII.2023, axca. (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/193591693>).
- **Pánama.** Coclé Province: El Valle de Antón, 8°36'35.2"N, 80°07'54.1"W, 594 m, 21.XI.2021, Kai SQUIRES. (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/101639344>).
- **Pánama.** Los Santos Province: Pocrí, 7°37'51.6"N 80°07'14.4"W, 49 m, 28.09.2020, Horacio PRADO. (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/61131135>).
- **Trinidad and Tobago.** Siparia: Avocat, 10°11'51.8"N 61°32'00.8"W, 24 m, 15.09.2023, Angeli PARASRAMSINGH. (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/183343672>).

Figure 3. Known occurrences of the taxon presumed to be *Sphex optimus*. Map SimpleMappr (<https://www.simplemappr.net/>).

DISCUSSION

Due to the cited sightings of multiple specimens that match the unusual color pattern of *S. optimus*, there seems to be a certain degree of consistency in these characters, so it can be concluded that the holotype was not merely an aberrant specimen. Thus, contrary to my original hypothesis, *S. optimus* is clearly not conspecific with *S. melanopus*, as females of the latter are devoid of ferruginous coloration on the metasoma, and the mesosomal tomentum is uniformly silvery in both sexes.

While species identification based solely on photographs is not feasible for every group, particularly among insects, I would argue that it is acceptable in this special case. Though several characters that are visible only under high magnification are used when identifying species of *Sphex*, they are mostly needed when dealing with specimens that

are uniformly dark in appearance. Otherwise, tomentum color is one of the best available features to distinguish members of the genus (DÖRFEL & OHL, 2022), and since sharply contrasting hues on the mesosoma are only known in a very small number of *Sphex* worldwide (one example being *Sphex pretiosus* DÖRFEL & OHL, 2015), the conspecificity of *S. optimus* with the taxon discussed here is very likely.

Nonetheless, having a specimen on hand for microscopic examination would obviously be ideal. It is conceivable that there is material of the species in the collection of the Insectopia Insect Museum, as it is situated in Puerto Jiménez (Costa Rica), less than 20 km away from one of the locations where an individual was observed. However, an inquiry to the museum has remained unanswered.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to express my gratitude to all the users cited in the records section. Without them sharing their photographs on *iNaturalist*, this discovery would not have been possible. Many thanks also go to Tanguy JEAN and Christian SCHMID-EGGER for reviewing the manuscript.

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ARTICLE

Lasioglossum inexpectatum sp. nov., a new species from Sardinia and Corsica (Hymenoptera: Apoidea: Halictidae)

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FLAMINIO, S., A. PAULY, G. CILIA, A. CORNUEL-WILLERMOZ, L. BORTOLOTTI & M. QUARANTA (2024). *Lasioglossum inexpectatum* sp. nov., a new species from Sardinia and Corsica (Hymenoptera: Apoidea: Halictidae). *Osmia*, 12: 23–32. <https://doi.org/10.47446/OSMIA12.4>

Abstract

Wild bee communities of Sardinia and Corsica, two Mediterranean islands, have been relatively understudied. In this article, *Lasioglossum inexpectatum* sp. nov., which is known exclusively in Sardinia and Corsica, is described, emphasizing the importance of ongoing research and conservation efforts to protect the unique wild bee biodiversity in the Mediterranean basin.

Keywords | Bees • endemic • Mediterranean basin • islands • integrative taxonomy

Lasioglossum inexpectatum sp. nov., une nouvelle espèce de Sardaigne et de Corse (Hymenoptera : Apoidea : Halictidae)

Résumé

Les populations d'abeilles sauvages de Sardaigne et de Corse, deux îles méditerranéennes, ont été relativement peu étudiées. Cet article décrit une nouvelle espèce, *Lasioglossum inexpectatum* sp. nov., connue exclusivement de Sardaigne et de Corse, montrant l'importance de poursuivre les efforts de recherche et de conservation pour protéger la biodiversité originale d'abeilles sauvages dans le Bassin méditerranéen.

Mots-clefs | Abeilles • endémique • Bassin méditerranéen • îles • taxonomie intégrative

Reçu • Received | 29 November 2023 || Accepté • Accepted | 06 August 2024 || Publié (en ligne) • Published (online) | 10 August 2024
Reviewers | P.-Y. MAESTRACCI • G. NÈVE • L. PLUME || <https://zoobank.org/A9FBC585-0CB1-42BF-8858-577D0D7A3FBA>

INTRODUCTION

Sardinia, despite being the second largest island in the Mediterranean Sea, has been little investigated in the past century concerning the fauna of Hymenoptera Apoidea. After the first investigations conducted by ALFKEN (1938),

GUIGLIA (1948), and GRANDI (1958), it was only towards the end of the last century that PROTA (1993), NOBILE (1995), NOBILE *et al.* (2000, 2005, 2015, 2016, 2021), MÜLLER (2012, 2018) and CATANIA *et al.* (2021) brought the number of

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species to 332 (REVERTÉ *et al.*, 2023). Of these, 74 species belong to the family Halictidae, including 36 of the genus *Lasioglossum* CURTIS, 1833. Only the subspecies *Lasioglossum nitidiusculum pseudocombinatum* BLÜTHGEN, 1921, distributed in the mountains of the island, is endemic to Sardinia.

Corsica, the fourth largest island in the Mediterranean and separated from Sardinia by 11 km of the Bonifacio Strait, has also been little studied from the perspective of wild bees. Despite the sampling efforts carried out by FERTON (1901a; 1901b) and the expeditions of the University of Mons (RASMONT, 1982; RASMONT & ADAMSKI, 1995; LECOCQ, 2006),

the work of MENEGUS (2018), the mission “Our Planet Reviewed – Corsica 2019-2021” (TOUROULT *et al.*, 2023) and the important inventory work led by the OCIC since 2017, knowledge of the bee fauna of Corsica remains incomplete, standing now at 309 species (REVERTÉ *et al.*, 2023). Of these, 72 species belong to the family Halictidae of which 43 are *Lasioglossum*, with *Lasioglossum corsicanum* BLÜTHGEN, 1931 and *L. aureimontanum* EBMER, 1970 being the only endemic species, both occurring in the mountains.

Herein, a new species, *Lasioglossum inexpectatum* sp. nov., only known from Sardinia and Corsica and probably endemic, is described using an integrative approach.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Morphological terminology follows MICHENER (2007). Specimens were measured from the vertical plane of the front of the head to the tip of the metasoma. The pictures of the lateral and dorsal habitus were taken using an Olympus E-M1 Mark I with an Olympus Zuiko 60 mm macro lens. Close-ups were taken with a Keyence microscope VHX-970F.

Molecular Analysis and DNA Barcode

Total DNA was extracted from the right hind leg (VILLALTA *et al.*, 2021). The hind legs were fully immersed in 1 mL of specific digestion buffer (CILIA *et al.*, 2022) in order to obtain a high quantity of mitochondrial DNA (FLAMINIO *et al.*, 2023a, 2023b) and incubated for 18 hours at 56 °C. As reported by CILIA *et al.* (2022), total DNA purification was performed using a phenol-chloroform extraction (Ultrapure™ Phenol:Chloroform:Isoamyl Alcohol, ThermoFisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) and the obtained DNAs were quantified using the spectrophotometer Infinite 200 PRO NanoQuant™ (TECAN Life Technologies, Männedorf, Switzerland) and stored at –20 °C until the analysis. Double-distilled Rnase-Dnase-free water was used as a negative control for all of these processes.

Amplification of mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) was performed using primer pairs able to amplify a 710-bp fragments within the highly conserved region coding for the Cytochrome C oxidase subunit I (COI) gene: LCO1490 (5' GGTCAACAAATCATAAAGATATTGG 3') and HC02198 (5' TAAACTTCAGGGTGACCAAAAAATCA 3') (FOLMER

et al., 1994). The PCR and amplicon visualization were performed. The obtained amplicons were purified using ExoSAP-IT Ex-press (ThermoFisher Scientific) and were then sequenced through the standard SANGER methodology. The obtained sequences were analysed using BioEdit (HALL, 1999) to create the consensus one aligning forward and reverse sequences and BLAST (using the megablast algorithm) (ALTSCHUL *et al.*, 1990).

To analyze the relationship with the other close species, we downloaded public sequences for *Lasioglossum nitidiusculum* (Accession number FBAPD651-11) and *L. parvulum* (Accession number FBHAP727-09) and produced a sequence for *L. transitorium* (Accession number OR800271). Then we aligned all the DNA sequences using ClustalW with the default parameters in MEGA ver. 11 (TAMURA *et al.* 2021). Based on the global similarity of the nucleotide sequences, we reconstructed a Neighbor-Joining (NJ) tree (SAITOU & NEI, 1987) with bootstrap replicates ($n = 1000$) (FELSENSTEIN, 1985). *Nomiapis diversipes* sequence (Accession number POLB023-23) was used as an outgroup.

Box A. Abbreviations

- SFC. Simone FLAMINIO Collection, Bologna, Italy
- OÖLM. Oberösterreichisches Landesmuseum, Linz, Austria
- CRASI. Collezione Riferimento Api Selvatiche d'Italia, CREA, Bologna, Italy
- CUSS. Collezione Università di Sassari, University of Sassari, Sassari, Italy
- OCIC. Observatoire Conservatoire des Invertébrés de Corse Collection, OCIC, Corte, France

RESULTS

Lasioglossum (Hemihalictus) inexpectatum sp. nov. FLAMINIO & PAULY, 2024

[Zoobank](https://zoobank.org/E9F8E138-0284-4261-A2BA-669B05266660) <https://zoobank.org/E9F8E138-0284-4261-A2BA-669B05266660>

Holotype

1 ♀, Italy, Sardinia, Sassari, Lago Baratz (40°41'22"N – 8°13'14"E), 30.IV.2022, on *Raphanus sativus*, leg. M. LEZZERI (OÖLM).

Paratypes

Idem holotype, 4 ♀♀ on *Raphanus sativus*, 2 ♀♀ on *Oxalis pes-caprae*, 1 ♀ on *Chrysanthemum coronarium*, 2 ♀♀ on *Malva sylvestris*, 1 ♀ on *Allium triquetrum*, leg. M. LEZZERI (SFC, CRASI, CUSS). 3 ♂♂, France, Corsica, Talasani, Figaretto, (47°24'48"N – 9°32'16"E), 08.VII.2020, leg. A. CORNUEL-WILLERMOZ (2 ♂♂ OCIC, 1 ♂ SFC). 1 ♂ France, Corsica, Vescovato, Terragliolo (42°31'27" N – 9°31'39"E), 30.VI.2020, leg. A. CORNUEL-WILLERMOZ, OÖLM.

Figure 1. *Lasioglossum inexpectatum* sp. nov., female. **A.** Dorsal habitus. **B.** Lateral habitus. **C.** Head (frontal view). **D.** Scutum. **e.** Propodeum. **F.** Spur of the hind tibia, **g** First tergum. Scale bar is 1 mm.

Description

Female

Body length 6 mm (figure 1a–b).

Head. Head (figure 1c) shorter than wide (length/width = 0.85), clypeus coarsely and densely punctate (interspaces 0.5–0.7 punctures diameter), the punctures slightly elongated and the underlying surface shiny. Supraclypeal area more densely punctate in the proximal half (interspaces 0.5 punctures diameter) than on the distal

half (interspaces at least 1 puncture diameter), underlying surface shiny. Frons densely and finely punctate. Vertex short and finely striated.

Mesosoma. Scutum and scutellum densely punctated, interspaces shagreened and equal to 1–2 points diameter (figure 1d). Propodeum not carinated, the horizontal part almost as long as the scutellum (propodeum/scutellum length = 0.94) and wrinkled in the proximal two-thirds, marginal part without wrinkles and slightly reboarded (figure 1e). Mesopleurae punctate, underlying

Figure 2. *Lasioglossum inexpectatum* sp. nov., male. a. Dorsal habitus. b. Lateral habitus. c. Head (frontal view). Scale bar is 1 mm.

Figure 3. *Lasioglossum inexpectatum* sp. nov., male. **a.** Abdomen. **b.** Sterna. **c.** First and second tergum. **d.** Scutum. **e.** Propodeum. **f.** Genitalia (frontal view). **g.** Genitalia (ventral view).

surface shiny. Legs black, hind tibial spur serrated (figure 1f).

Metasoma. The marginal part of the terga slightly translucent and brownish. The first tergum shiny, and almost impunctate on the disc, the center of the marginal part being slightly depressed and more densely but very delicately punctate (interspaces 1–1.5 punctures diameter), punctures becoming sparser in the center (figure 1g). Following terga shiny and more densely punctate, on the disc interspaces equal to less than one point diameter; the marginal part less densely punctate, and interspaces equal to several puncture diameter.

Male

Body length 5.5 mm (figure 2a–b).

Head. Head (figure 2c) as long as wide (length/width = 1), clypeus densely and coarsely punctate (interspaces

less than 0.5 punctures diameter), yellow in the apical third. Labrum also yellow, and mandibles yellowish only in the middle. Frons densely and delicately punctate, vertex short and shiny. Antennae moderately long, flagellomeres as long as wide (length/width = 1), underside ochraceous; scape and pedicel black.

Mesosoma. Scutum and scutellum (figure 3d) densely punctate (interspaces equal to 0.5–1 puncture diameter), underlying surface shiny. Propodeum not carinated, the horizontal part clearly shorter than the scutellum (length/width = 0.58), wrinkled all over, and shiny (figure 3e). Mesopleurae punctate, underlying surface shiny. Basitarsus and following tarsomeres of all legs yellowish, and basal and apical parts of the tibia also yellowish.

Metasoma. Marginal part of the terga slightly translucent and brownish (figure 3c). The first tergum

Figure 4. Locus typicus of *Lasioglossum inexpectatum* sp. nov.: Lago Baratz, Sardinia, Italy (55 m a.s.l.).

shiny, sparsely punctate on the disc, and more densely punctate in the apical margin (figure 3a). Following terga more densely and uniformly punctate (interspaces less than 1 puncture diameter), apical margin almost impunctate and horizontally shagreened. Sterna with erect whitish hairs (figure 3b). Gonostyli small and pointed (figure 3f), membranous lobe of gonocoxite short, broad and rounded (figure 3g).

Diagnosis

Lasioglossum inexpectatum sp. nov. can be assigned to the subgenus *Hemihalictus* COCKERELL, 1897 by the propodeum not carinated with the horizontal part not sloping directly into the vertical part and by the black integument. The closest taxa, considering the distribution areal, are *L. nitidiusculum* KIRBY, 1802, *L. parvulum* SCHENCK, 1853, and *L. transitorium* SCHENCK, 1868. *Lasioglossum nitidiusculum* and *L. parvulum* can be separated, in the female sex, by the shiny cuticle of the scutum, which is instead shagreened and less densely punctate in *L. inexpectatum* sp. nov., and by the shorter and differently sculptured basal part of the propodeum. Furthermore, the first tergum of *L. nitidiusculum* is more densely punctate than in *L. inexpectatum* sp. nov. Male specimens can be easily separated by the tufts of hairs on the sterna of *L. nitidiusculum*, absent in *L. inexpectatum* sp. nov., and by the clearly different gonostyli and membranous lobe. *L. transitorium* can be separated, in the female sex, mainly for the longer head, the shiny cuticle of the scutum, and the spur of the hind tibia with semi-columnar processes. The male sex can be separated by the longer head, the labrum black, and the differences in the shape of the gonostyli and the membranous lobe.

Distribution and ecology

Lasioglossum inexpectatum is known only from Sardinia (Italy) and Corsica (France). The type locality,

Lago Baratz (Sassari, 56 m a.s.l., figure 4), is the only natural Sardinia basin. The collection site (Lago Baratz) is characterized by a typical Mediterranean shrub habitat, featuring sclerophyllous species. In the more open grassy areas, species such as *Pistacia lentiscus* L., *Phillyrea angustifolia* L., *Arbutus unedo* L., and *Erica arborea* L. are found, while in the understory consisting of *Juniperus phoenicea* L. and *Quercus ilex* L., shrubs like *Ruscus aculeatus* L., *Clematis flammula* L., and *Asparagus acutifolius* L. are widespread.

Additionally, in the outermost zone of Lago Baratz, a pine reforestation (*Pinus pinea* L., *Pinus halepensis* MILLER) was planted in the 1950s, along with *Eucalyptus* and *Robinia* (BORGARELLO *et al.*, 2000). The habitat vegetation was confirmed by floristic surveys in the field at the time of captures. All female specimens were collected in April by aerial net while visiting flowers of *Raphanus raphanistrum* L. subsp. *sativus* (L.) SCHMALH. (Brassicaceae), *Oxalis pes-caprae* L. (Oxalidaceae), *Malva sylvestris* L. (Malvaceae), *Allium triquetrum* L. (Amaryllidaceae) and *Glebionis coronaria* (L.) SPACH (= *Chrysanthemum coronarium* L.) (Asteraceae). Males were also collected by aerial net in Terragliolo, a Mediterranean scrub close to Golo River in June, and in Talassani, a coastal dunal system in July. Interestingly, unlike other species and subspecies endemic to the two islands, *L. inexpectatum* seems to be present only at low altitudes (Figure 5). The map in Figure 7 shows the collecting locations.

Molecular analysis

High-quality DNA sequences were obtained from one female specimens (Accession number OR807151) and one of the male specimens (Accession number OR807152). Sequences obtained were used as queries in the BOLD-IS tool and then blasted on *GenBank*, returning a partial match with *L. nitidiusculum* (identity percentage 94.92 %, E-value 0^{-180}) and *L. parvulum* (88.98 %, E-value 4^{-180}) sequences deposited

on *GenBank*. In Figure 6, the neighbor-joining tree, showing the relationships between male and female specimens of *L. inexpectatum* and other related species of *Lasioglossum* (*Hemihalictus*), is reported. The bootstrap is indicated on the branches.

Derivatio nominis

From the Latin adjective *inexpectatum* (unexpected), because of the stupor of the discovery of this new species in Europe.

Figure 5. Collecting site of the male of *L. inexpectatum* sp. nov., Vescovato (Corsica, France, 46 m a.s.l.).

Figure 6. Neighbor-Joining tree, showing the relationships between *L. inexpectatum* sp. nov. and other related species of *Lasioglossum* (*Hemihalictus*). The percentage of replicate trees in which the associated taxa clustered together in the bootstrap test (1000 replicates) are shown above the branches. The evolutionary distances were computed using the Maximum Composite Likelihood method. This analysis involved 6 nucleotide sequences.

Figure 20. Map showing the finding localities of *Lasioglossum inexpectatum*. Map QGIS version 3.1.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The discovery of *Lasioglossum inexpectatum* adds to the evidence that there is still a taxonomic gap in Europe regarding Hymenoptera Apoidea (GHISBAIN *et al.*, 2023a; GHISBAIN *et al.*, 2023b; PRAZ & BÉNON, 2023; PRAZ *et al.*, 2022;

WOOD, 2022, 2023; WOOD & LE DIVELEC, 2022; WOOD *et al.*, 2022) and that further research expeditions and projects aimed at deepening the fauna especially of southern Europe are necessary.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This study was supported by the project *BeeNet* (Italian National Fund under FEASR 2014-2020) from the Italian Ministry of Agriculture and Food Sovereignty and Forestry (MASAF). The authors would also like to thank Rosa RANALLI for her help in outlining the habitat vegetation of Lago Baratz.

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ARTICLE

Découverte de *Linepithema humile* (MAYR, 1868) sur l'île de la Réunion (France) et nouvelle mention pour l'espèce *Cyphomyrmex minutus* MAYR, 1862 avec inclusion géoréférencée des espèces rencontrées (Hymenoptera : Formicidae : Myrmicinae)

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COLINDRE, L. (2024). Découverte de *Linepithema humile* (MAYR, 1868) sur l'île de la Réunion (France) et nouvelle mention pour l'espèce *Cyphomyrmex minutus* MAYR, 1862 avec inclusion géoréférencée des espèces rencontrées (Hymenoptera : Formicidae : Myrmicinae). *Osmia*, 12: 33–36. <https://doi.org/10.47446/OSMIA12.5>

Résumé

Nous signalons pour la première fois la présence de la fourmi d'Argentine *Linepithema humile* (MAYR, 1868), sur l'île de la Réunion et précisons les conditions dans lesquelles nous l'avons détectée. Nous mentionnons également la seconde observation pour la fourmi *Cyphomyrmex minutus* MAYR, 1862.

Mots-clefs | Fourmi d'Argentine • Fourmi champignoniste • Myrmicinae • Océan Indien • Mascareignes

Discovery of *Linepithema humile* (MAYR, 1868) on Reunion Island (France) and new record for the species *Cyphomyrmex minutus* MAYR, 1862 with georeferenced inclusion of found species (Hymenoptera: Formicidae: Myrmicinae)

Abstract

We report for the first time the presence of the Argentine ant *Linepithema humile* (MAYR, 1868) on Reunion Island and specify the conditions under which we detected it. We also mention the second observation for the ant *Cyphomyrmex minutus* MAYR, 1862.

Keywords | Argentine ant • Leafcutter ant • Myrmicinae • Indian Ocean • Mascarenes Islands

Reçu • Received | 21 October 2023 || Accepté • Accepted | 13 August 2024 || Publié (en ligne) • Published (online) | 15 August 2024

Reviewers | L. GOMEL • T. JEAN || <https://zoobank.org/DC167568-2D4B-40FC-A1C2-6662B92F53D7>

Preprint on Zenodo | 29 November 2023 | <https://zenodo.org/records/10223027>

INTRODUCTION

Les informations sont encore très parcellaires concernant les Hyménoptères Formicidae de l'île de la Réunion. Les inventaires dédiés aux fourmis sont anciens : seulement quatre au XIX^{ème} siècle (FOREL, 1886, 1891, 1895 ; EMERY, 1895) et deux au XX^{ème} siècle (DONISTHORPE, 1946 ; MAMET, 1954). Les travaux contemporains restent tout aussi rares sur le sujet (BLARD *et al.*, 2003 ; BLARD, 2006 ; PARNAUDEAU & MADL, 2009). Les connaissances actuelles sur la myrmécofaune de l'île se caractérisent par un cortège relativement restreint : on dénombre 46 espèces dont plus de 70 % sont introduites (ANTWEB, 2023).

Sur la liste des six espèces envahissantes les plus répandues et ayant un impact reconnu sur les habitats qu'elles colonisent (HOLWAY *et al.*, 2002), trois sont présentes sur

l'île : *Anoplolepis gracilipes* (SMITH, 1857) introduite antérieurement à 1895 (FOREL, 1895), *Pheidole megacephala* (FABRICIUS, 1793) et *Solenopsis geminata* (FABRICIUS, 1804) introduites toutes les deux antérieurement à 1954 (MAMET, 1954). Les trois autres espèces citées par HOLWAY *et al.* (2002) représentent une menace sérieuse pour l'île et toute la péninsule des Mascareignes tant leur déplacement est facilité par les flux commerciaux internationaux (UICN-SSC, 2004), toujours plus nombreux et plus rapides : il s'agit de *Solenopsis invicta* BUREN, 1972, *Wasmannia auropunctata* (ROGER, 1863) et *Linepithema humile* (MAYR, 1868).

Le présent article relate deux découvertes réalisées en août 2023 lors d'une prospection sur l'île de la Réunion et se complète d'une liste des espèces observées.

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DÉCOUVERTE DE LA FOURMI D'ARGENTINE *LINEPITHEMA HUMILE*

C'est lors d'un prélèvement sur l'île le 2 août 2023 qu'un nid de fourmi d'Argentine *Linepithema humile* (MAYR, 1868) (figure 1) a été détecté dans la commune du Tampon à environ 1200–1300 m d'altitude [– 21,216 ; 55,552]. Le nid est localisé au pied d'un établissement hôtelier implanté depuis plusieurs décennies, avec des fourrageuses particulièrement actives par 17 °C. Un matériel de 14 ouvrières (*in coll.* L. COLINDRE) a été rapporté à des fins d'identification en laboratoire. L'utilisation de la révision taxonomique du genre *Linepithema* (WILD, 2007) ainsi qu'une contre-expertise sur plusieurs exemplaires (Dr Benoît GUÉNARD, Insect Biodiversity and Biogeography Lab, Université de Hong-Kong) confirment la détermination de cette espèce.

Originnaire d'Amérique du Sud (TSUTSUI *et al.*, 2001), l'espèce s'est répandue dans de nombreux pays à la suite d'activités anthropiques (SUAREZ *et al.*, 2001). Selon ROURA-PASCUAL *et al.* (2004), les conditions climatiques tropicales de l'océan Indien laissaient à penser que les possibilités d'implantation

de la fourmi d'Argentine à la Réunion restaient faibles. D'ailleurs, la présence de cette fourmi dans les Mascareignes n'avait encore jamais été signalée (*comm. pers.* B. GUÉNARD, 2023). Il est donc très probable que l'espèce se soit implantée très récemment, c'est-à-dire entre les derniers inventaires du début des années 2000 et aujourd'hui.

Dans certaines régions du globe, l'espèce est tolérante aux températures plus basses comprises entre 9,8 et 13,5 °C (RUSSEL COLE *et al.*, 1992)² et s'accommode de variations hygrométriques plus importantes que les autres espèces (MENKE & HOLWAY, 2006). À la Réunion, qui réunit tous ces facteurs abiotiques, elle pourrait donc facilement s'y développer (BLARD, 2006). Une fois répandue, son éradication serait alors quasi-impossible. Quant aux méthodes de contrôle, elles s'avèrent coûteuses et souvent inefficaces (ANGULO *et al.*, 2022). Nous ne savons pas à ce stade si cette implantation reste localisée ou d'ampleur, mais la colonie d'origine nécessiterait une destruction des nids selon la méthode inspirée d'INOUE *et al.* (2015).

Figure 1. *Linepithema humile* (MAYR, 1868). Ouvrière de profil.
Photo M. ESPOSITO. Spécimen CASENT0281314 Antweb. <https://www.antweb.org>

REDÉCOUVERTE DE LA FOURMI CHAMPIGNONNISTE *CYPHOMYRMEX MINUTUS*

La minuscule (1,8–2,1 mm) fourmi champignonniste *Cyphomyrmex minutus* MAYR, 1862 (figures 2–3) a été identifiée sur le littoral sud de l'île, sur la commune de Grande-Anse [– 21,370 ; 55,552], le 12 août 2023, au sol et

dans un contexte boisé. Cette seconde observation vient confirmer son implantation durable à la Réunion. La première mention due à B. L. FISHER (*in site* ANTWEB, 2023) provenait d'un jardin de Sainte-Anne [– 21.06541 ; 55.73206]

² Dans le nid et sous conditions expérimentales, le thermo-préférendum pour le bon développement des œufs se situe à 26 °C. En revanche, les températures hautes (supérieures à 32 °C) affectent négativement le couvain. *In natura*, le gradient thermique présent à l'intérieur du nid reste sous influence des températures instables tout au long de la journée (ABRIL *et al.*, 2010).

à l'est de l'île et datait du 30 mars 2011. Elle est par ailleurs inconnue des îles les plus proches : Maurice, Rodrigues et Madagascar.

Appartenant à la tribu des Attini SMITH, 1858, sous-famille des Myrmicinae LEPELETIER, 1835, l'espèce est très loin de son aire d'origine : elle est en effet native du Nouveau Continent, répandue dans les îles Caraïbes ainsi qu'en Amérique du Nord, centrale et du Sud (JANICKI *et al.*, 2023). La présence

d'un isolat sur l'île de la Réunion intrigue et interroge car, à ce stade, c'est la seule région où cette espèce est connue en dehors du continent américain dont elle provient. Ce constat est étonnant car les Attini ne sont pas spécialement connus pour leur propension à coloniser de nouvelles régions aussi éloignées de leur territoire d'origine (*comm. pers.* B. GUENARD, 2023). De ce point de vue, cette fourmi doit être considérée comme une espèce atypique et singulière au sein de l'entomofaune réunionnaise.

Figure 2. *Cyphomyrmex minutus* MAYR, 1862. Ouvrière, tête vue de face. Photo M. ESPOSITO. Spécimen CASENT0264753 Antweb. <https://www.antweb.org>

Figure 3. *Cyphomyrmex minutus* MAYR, 1862. Ouvrière de profil. Photo M. ESPOSITO. Spécimen CASENT0264753 Antweb. <https://www.antweb.org>

LISTE DES AUTRES ESPÈCES RENCONTRÉES

Tableau I. Liste des espèces identifiées sur l'île de la Réunion (France).

Abréviations : **Dpt** = Département. **Fam.** = Famille (**D** = Dolichoderinae ; **F** = Formicinae ; **M** = Myrmicinae ; **P** = Ponerinae). **Coll.** = Collection (numérotation prélèvement).

Espèces	Dpt	Communes	Dates	Fam.	Latitude	Longitude	N° Coll.	Code INPN
<i>Anoplolepis gracilipes</i> (SMITH, 1857)	974	Saint-Philippe	12/08/2023	F	- 21,281	55,795	11	264513
<i>Brachymyrmex gr. cordemoyi</i> FOREL, 1895 ³	974	Hell-Bourg	11/08/2023	F	- 21,067	55,515	1-2	643206
<i>Brachymyrmex gr. cordemoyi</i> FOREL, 1895 ³	974	Saint-Louis	14/08/2023	F	- 21,191	55,448	22	643206
<i>Cyphomyrmex minutus</i> MAYR, 1862	974	Grande-Anse	12/08/2023	M	- 21,370	55,552	18	721014
<i>Hypoponera ludovicæ</i> (FOREL, 1892)	974	Saint-Joseph	13/08/2023	P	- 21,208	55,644	14	643211
<i>Hypoponera eduardi</i> (FOREL, 1894)	974	Saint-Paul	14/08/2023	P	- 21,074	55,388	25	219528
<i>Linepithema humile</i> (MAYR, 1868)	974	Le Tampon	12/08/2023	D	- 21,216	55,552	13	219464
<i>Monomorium floricola</i> (JERDON, 1851)	974	Saint-Gilles	14/08/2023	M	- 21,091	55,231	27	589997
<i>Monomorium floricola</i> (JERDON, 1851)	974	Saint-Louis	14/08/2023	M	- 21,191	55,448	23	589997
<i>Nylanderia bourbonica</i> (FOREL, 1886)	974	Hell-Bourg	11/08/2023	F	- 21,067	55,515	3	642439
<i>Paratrechina longicornis</i> (LATREILLE, 1802)	974	Saint-Gilles	14/08/2023	F	- 21,091	55,231	26	219480
<i>Pheidole megacephala</i> (FABRICIUS, 1793)	974	Grande-Anse	12/08/2023	M	- 21,370	55,552	19	219383
<i>Pheidole megacephala</i> (FABRICIUS, 1793)	974	Hell-Bourg	11/08/2023	M	- 21,067	55,515	4	643206
<i>Pheidole megacephala</i> (FABRICIUS, 1793)	974	Sainte-Rose	12/08/2023	M	- 21,185	55,827	8	643206
<i>Pheidole megacephala</i> (FABRICIUS, 1793)	974	Saint-Louis	14/08/2023	M	- 21,091	55,231	27	219383
<i>Solenopsis geminata</i> (FABRICIUS, 1804)	974	Grande-Anse	12/08/2023	M	- 21,371	55,550	16-17	264070
<i>Solenopsis geminata</i> (FABRICIUS, 1804)	974	Sainte-Rose	12/08/2023	M	- 21,185	55,827	9-10	264070
<i>Solenopsis geminata</i> (FABRICIUS, 1804)	974	Saint-Joseph	13/08/2023	M	- 21,208	55,644	15	264070
<i>Solenopsis geminata</i> (FABRICIUS, 1804)	974	Saint-Philippe	12/08/2023	M	- 21,374	55,711	12	264070
<i>Tapinoma melanocephalum</i> (FABRICIUS, 1793)	974	Saint-Gilles	14/08/2023	D	- 21,091	55,231	26	264322
<i>Tapinoma melanocephalum</i> (FABRICIUS, 1793)	974	Bras-Panon	12/08/2023	D	- 21,000	55,687	6	264322
<i>Tapinoma melanocephalum</i> (FABRICIUS, 1793)	974	Saint-Louis	14/08/2023	D	- 21,191	55,448	24	264322
<i>Technomyrmex pallipes</i> (SMITH, 1876)	974	Bras-Panon	12/08/2023	D	- 21,000	55,687	5	643223
<i>Technomyrmex sp.</i>	974	Bras-Panon	12/08/2023	D	- 21,000	55,687	7	-

³ *B. cordemoyi* présente, selon plusieurs études, une importante variation intraspécifique pouvant inclure plusieurs espèces (ORTIZ-SEPULVEDA *et al.*, 2019 ; HUSEMANN *et al.*, 2019). Nous retenons donc ici un groupe d'espèces (abréviation « gr. ») dans l'attente d'études phylogénétiques complémentaires.

REMERCIEMENTS

J'adresse mes plus sincères remerciements au Dr Benoît GUÉNARD pour la lecture de cet article et la vérification des échantillons confiés. Merci aux reviewers, Luc GOMEL et Tanguy JEAN, ainsi qu'à Mehdi ISSERTES pour la mise en forme. Je salue également nos guides réunionnais, Rémi-Paul et Mélissa, naturalistes engagés au service de leur île. Bien que trop courte, ce fut une bien belle rencontre.

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ARTICLE

Première liste des espèces d'abeilles de la région Centre-Val de Loire (France) déclinée par départements sur la période 1990-2021 (Hymenoptera : Apoidea : Anthophila)

Philippe BOURLET¹

BOURLET, P. (2024). Première liste des espèces d'abeilles de la région Centre-Val de Loire (France) déclinée par départements sur la période 1990-2021 (Hymenoptera : Apoidea : Anthophila). *Osmia*, 12: 37–46. <https://doi.org/10.47446/OSMIA12.6>

Résumé

Cet article présente la liste taxonomique des abeilles de la région Centre-Val de Loire (France), déclinée par départements, sur la période 1990-2021. Cette étude met en évidence la présence de 287 espèces d'abeilles dans cette région avec des disparités départementales : entre 50 à 60 espèces sont recensées dans l'Indre et l'Eure-et-Loir contre près de 200 espèces dans le Loiret (182) et le Loir-et-Cher (195). Ces résultats constituent donc une incitation à développer la connaissance de la faune d'abeilles de notre région.

Mots-clefs | UICN • Cher • Eure-et-Loir • Indre • Indre-et-Loire • Loir-et-Cher • Loiret • Apiformes • abeilles sauvages

First list of bee species of the Centre-Val de Loire region (France) declined by departments over the period 1990–2021. (Hymenoptera: Apoidea: Anthophila)

Abstract

This article presents the taxonomic list of bees in the Centre-Val de Loire region (France) by department over the period 1990–2021. This study reveals the presence of 287 bee species in the region, with disparities between departments: between 50 and 60 species are recorded in Indre and Eure-et-Loir, compared with almost 200 species in Loiret (182) and Loir-et-Cher (195). These results are meant as an encouragement to develop our knowledge of the bee fauna in our region.

Keywords | IUCN • Cher • Eure-et-Loir • Indre • Indre-et-Loire • Loir-et-Cher • Loiret • Apiformes • wild bees

Reçu • Received | 18 December 2022 || Accepté • Accepted | 13 December 2024 || Publié (en ligne) • Published (online) | 15 December 2024
Reviewers | B. GESLIN • T. JEAN || <https://zoobank.org/3397AC62-4C25-4F2A-BE18-0FB2D8CB944B>

INTRODUCTION

Au printemps 2016, la ministre en charge de l'environnement lançait le Plan National d'Actions « France, Terre de pollinisateurs » (GADOUM & ROUX-FOUILLET, 2016) avec l'ambition d'enrayer le déclin de ces insectes pollinisateurs et de maintenir leurs populations.

Pour répondre à cet objectif et définir des actions de conservation à mener, ce PNA insiste sur l'importance de connaître la répartition, la distribution et l'abondance des espèces d'insectes pollinisateurs sauvages sur le territoire (axe 1, action 1). C'est dans ce contexte que la réalisation de la première liste régionale par départements des espèces d'abeilles de la région Centre-Val de Loire (CVL) est décidée fin 2018, comme déclinaison régionale du plan national.

Il s'agit d'un travail :

- animé par Caroline LE BRIS initialement puis Axelle MARCHANT (1) désormais, de l'association Hommes et Territoires (H&T) ;
- et piloté par François MICHEAU initialement puis Frédéric SANCHIS (2) désormais, de la DREAL CVL.

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Un comité d'experts a par ailleurs été constitué. Il est composé d'Adrien CHOREIN (Conservatoire d'Espaces Naturels Centre-Val de Loire), Jean-Louis PRATZ (CERCOPE), Jean-David CHAPELIN-VISCARDI (Laboratoire d'éco-entomologie d'Orléans), Michel BINON (Muséum d'Orléans

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pour la Biodiversité et l'Environnement), Serge GRESSETTE (Conservatoire d'espaces naturels Centre-Val de Loire), Mathieu WILLMES (DREAL), Mathilde BAUDE (Université d'Orléans) et Philippe BOURLET.

Le présent article présente les premiers résultats de cette étude qui pourra servir de base pour de futurs travaux, comme l'élaboration de listes rouges ou encore de listes d'espèces déterminantes ZNIEFF.

MATÉRIEL ET MÉTHODES

La présente liste régionale des espèces d'abeilles a été établie à partir de 17 350 données s'étalant sur la période 1990-2021 (incluant quelques données de 2022). Ces données sont issues de sources variées :

- Données institutionnelles et associatives : Système d'Information de l'Inventaire du Patrimoine Naturel SINP (incluant les données de BAILEY, 2014), CERCOPE et Nature 18 ;
- Données d'études scientifiques (VILLALTA *et al.*, 2022 ; LE FÉON, 2010) ;
- Données compilées par Christian COCQUEMPOT pour l'Indre et Loire ;

- Données personnelles (par ordre alphabétique : Philippe BOURLET, Serge GADOUM, Bernard LEMESLE, Benoît MARTHA).

Pour la production de cette liste, les données retenues l'ont été selon les critères suivants :

- pour les spécimens d'espèces courantes, ubiquistes, « faciles » à identifier (voir tableau I), l'identification par un seul déterminateur était suffisante.
- pour les spécimens de toutes les autres espèces, de loin les plus nombreuses, l'identification devait être obligatoirement réalisée par au moins deux personnes, dont un expert du genre.

RÉSULTATS : LISTE DES ESPÈCES D'ABEILLES DE LA RÉGION CENTRE-VAL DE LOIRE OBTENUE

La liste régionale des abeilles de la région Centre-Val de Loire contient 287 espèces listées dans le tableau I au sein duquel on trouvera :

- le nom des espèces ;
- les espèces retenues comme ubiquistes, courantes, « faciles » à identifier ;
- le nombre indicatif d'occurrences observées par espèce dans la région et dans la période retenue ;
- le statut de l'UICN issu de l'*European Red List of Bees* (NIETO *et al.*, 2014) ;
- la présence départementale, avec la date des premières et dernières occurrences, pour chacun des six départements.

La liste des 287 espèces présentes en région CVL représente environ 29 % des espèces nationales. Ce pourcentage est similaire pour chaque famille d'abeilles, sauf en ce qui concerne les Apidae présentant une proportion (23 %) légèrement inférieure aux 29 % observés pour l'ensemble de la liste.

Disparités entre les départements

Cette première liste, déclinée par départements, montre également une disparité assez importante du nombre d'espèces relevées dans les 6 départements étudiés (figure 1). Par exemple, dans l'Indre et l'Eure-et-Loir, on ne dénombre, à l'issue de ce travail, que 50 à 60 espèces, alors que d'autres départements, comme le Loiret et le Loir-et-Cher, sont nettement plus renseignés, avec respectivement 182 et 195 espèces recensées. Cela s'explique, pour ces deux départements, par les études scientifiques qui y ont été réalisées ces dernières années (BAILEY, 2014 ; LE FÉON, 2010 ; VILLALTA *et al.*, 2022).

Des espèces à protéger en Centre-Val de Loire

Les espèces régionales identifiées se répartissent comme suit selon leur statut UICN européen de conservation :

- **DD** (données insuffisantes) : 59 espèces.

Figure 1. Nombre d'espèces d'abeilles recensées par département (ronds bleus) dans la région Centre-Val de Loire. Le nom des départements est indiqué en capitales et le nom des chefs-lieux en minuscules. Fond de carte : <http://cartefrance.blogspot.com>

- **LC** (préoccupation mineure) : 199 espèces.
- **NT** (quasi menacée) : 23 espèces.
- **VU** (vulnérable) : 2 espèces, à savoir *Bombus muscorum* (36) et *Colletes fodiens* (41).
- **EN** (en danger) : 2 espèces, à savoir *Nomada pulchra* (37) et *Trachusa interrupta* (37, 41).
- **Non répertoriées** dans la liste UICN : 2 espèces, à savoir *Dasyglossum morawitzi* (37) et *Lasioglossum medinai* (41, 45).

Trois espèces d'abeilles de cette liste régionale sont considérées comme déterminantes ZNIEFF en région Centre-Val de Loire (COLLECTIF, 2018) : ce sont les bourdons *Bombus humilis*, *Bombus ruderatus* et *Bombus sylvarum*.

Des données historiques

Au cours du travail de production de cette liste, nous avons collecté 35 données historiques, datant d'avant 1990, correspondant à 29 espèces (tableau II).

Figure 2. Femelle de *Dasygaster argyrea* butinant une scabieuse en Indre-et-Loire (Puy Besnard, Chinon). Photo P. BOURLET (août 2017).

Tableau I. Liste des espèces d'abeilles de la région Centre-Val de Loire sur la période 1990-2021.

Nom de l'espèce (TaxRef v15)	Statut UICN Europe 2015	Espèces ubiquistes et/ou courantes et/ou faciles à identifier	Nombre d'occurrences en Centre-Val de Loire	Nombre d'espèces par département					
				Cher (18)	Eure-et-Loir (28)	Indre (36)	Indre-et-Loire (37)	Loir-et-Cher (41)	Loiret (45)
				50	58	156	195	182	50
<i>Aglaopis tridentata</i> (NYLANDER, 1848)	LC		2					2011	2017
<i>Ammobates punctatus</i> (FABRICIUS, 1804)	LC		1					2014	
<i>Andrena agilissima</i> (SCOPOLI, 1770)	DD		11			2010-2017	1994-2019	2012-2017	
<i>Andrena alfkenella</i> PERKINS, 1914	DD		2					2007-2010	
<i>Andrena angustior</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	DD		111	2011			2017	2010-2012	2011
<i>Andrena apicata</i> SMITH, 1847	DD		17	2011					2011
<i>Andrena barbilabris</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	DD		4				2017	2016	2017
<i>Andrena bicolor</i> FABRICIUS, 1775	LC	X	237	2011-2021	2017-2021			2008-2017	2011
<i>Andrena bimaculata</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	DD		17				1995		2011
<i>Andrena bucephala</i> STEPHENS, 1846	DD		42	2011					2011
<i>Andrena carantonica</i> PÉREZ, 1902	DD		144	2011			2017	2007-2011	2011
<i>Andrena chrysoseles</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	DD		63	2011				2007	2011
<i>Andrena cineraria</i> (LINNAEUS, 1758)	LC	X	267	2011-(2022)	2008-2017	2018	1993-2020	2007-2021	2011-(2022)
<i>Andrena clarkella</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	DD		4						2011
<i>Andrena decipiens</i> SCHENCK, 1861	DD		7	2011				2007-2011	
<i>Andrena denticulata</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	DD		2				2014	2011	
<i>Andrena distinguenda</i> SCHENCK, 1871	DD		2					2007-2010	
<i>Andrena dorsata</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	DD		172	2011-2020	2018-2021		1991-2017	2007-2020	2011

<i>Andrena falsifica</i> PERKINS, 1915	DD		1							2017
<i>Andrena ferox</i> SMITH, 1847	DD		20	2011						2011
<i>Andrena flavipes</i> PANZER, 1799	LC	X	581	2008-(2022)	2015-2021	2004-2008	2011-2014	2006-(2022)		2007-2017
<i>Andrena florea</i> FABRICIUS, 1793	DD	X	37	2012-2021	2017	2017-2019	2011-2014	2010-2020		2011-2017
<i>Andrena fucata</i> SMITH, 1847	DD		2					2007		2011
<i>Andrena fulva</i> (MÜLLER, 1766)	DD	X	223	2009-(2022)	2012-2021	2005-2018	2010-2011	2007-2020		2011
<i>Andrena fulvago</i> (CHRIST, 1791)	DD		18	2011			1995-2017			2011
<i>Andrena fulvata</i> STOECKERT, 1930	DD		261	2011			2010-2017	2007-2011		2011
<i>Andrena fuscipes</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	DD		2					2007		2011
<i>Andrena gravida</i> IMHOFF, 1832	DD	X	127	2011-2021	2018-2021	2010		2007-2020		2011
<i>Andrena haemorrhoea</i> (FABRICIUS, 1781)	LC	X	563	2008-2021	2012-2021	2018	2004-2013	2007-(2022)		2011-(2022)
<i>Andrena hattorfiana</i> (FABRICIUS, 1775)	NT		11		2020-2021		2010	2015-2018		
<i>Andrena helvola</i> (LINNAEUS, 1758)	DD		224	2011				2017		2011-2017
<i>Andrena labialis</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	DD		1							2017
<i>Andrena labiata</i> FABRICIUS, 1781	DD		2	2020				2009-2019		
<i>Andrena lagopus</i> LATREILLE, 1809	LC		23	2012-2021			2017	2007-2020		2011
<i>Andrena lathyri</i> ALFKEN, 1898	DD		2					2020		
<i>Andrena marginata</i> FABRICIUS, 1777	DD		1					2011		
<i>Andrena minutula</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	DD		74				1990-2017	2007-2017		2017
<i>Andrena minutuloides</i> PERKINS, 1914	DD		17				1991-1995	2010-2017		2017
<i>Andrena mitis</i> SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1883	DD		13							2011
<i>Andrena nana</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	LC		1				1991			
<i>Andrena nigroaenea</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	LC	X	270	2020	2012-2021		1995-2017	2007-2017		2011-2017
<i>Andrena nigroolivacea</i> DOURS, 1873	LC		3				2017			2017
<i>Andrena nitida</i> (MÜLLER, 1776)	LC	X	303	2008-2020	2012-2021		2010-2011	2007-2017		2017
<i>Andrena ovatula</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	NT		18	2011			2012			2011
<i>Andrena pandellei</i> PÉREZ, 1895	LC		42	2011-2020			2010-2021	2006-(2022)		2011
<i>Andrena pilipes</i> FABRICIUS, 1781	LC		19	2011			2011-2021	2007-2010		2011
<i>Andrena praecox</i> (SCOPOLI, 1763)	LC		35	2011						2017
<i>Andrena propinqua</i> SCHENCK, 1853	DD		1				2010			
<i>Andrena proxima</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	DD		7					2017		2017
<i>Andrena pusilla</i> PÉREZ, 1903	DD		1							2011
<i>Andrena ranunculi</i> SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1884	LC		1	2014						
<i>Andrena rhenana</i> STOECKERT, 1930	DD		14	2011				2017		2017
<i>Andrena rosae</i> PANZER, 1801	DD		5							2011
<i>Andrena rufula</i> SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1883	LC		50	2011						2011-2017
<i>Andrena semilaevis</i> PÉREZ, 1903	DD		46				2017			2017
<i>Andrena similis</i> SMITH, 1849	DD		4	2011			2007-2010			2011
<i>Andrena simontornyella</i> NOSKIEWICZ, 1939	LC		11				2017	2011-2012		2017
<i>Andrena strohmella</i> STOECKERT, 1928	LC		15				2014	2007		2011
<i>Andrena synadelpha</i> PERKINS, 1914	DD		2	2011						
<i>Andrena trimmerana</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	LC		44	2008-2011			1990-2014	2007-2017		2011-2017
<i>Andrena vaga</i> PANZER, 1799	LC		19	2013	2020-2022		2010-2017	2014-2019		2017
<i>Andrena varians</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	LC		7	2011						2011
<i>Andrena ventralis</i> IMHOFF, 1832	DD		34				2017			2011-2017
<i>Andrena viridescens</i> VIREECK, 1916	DD		3	2020			2017	2012		
<i>Andrena wilkella</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	DD		1							2011
<i>Anthidiellum strigatum</i> (PANZER, 1805)	LC		2	2009-2015				2016		
<i>Anthidium florentinum</i> (FABRICIUS, 1775)	LC		1							2017
<i>Anthidium manicatum</i> (LINNAEUS, 1758)	LC	X	61	2008-2021	2017	2018	1990-2017	2008-2020		2017
<i>Anthidium oblongatum</i> (ILIGER, 1806)	LC		2	2008			2021			
<i>Anthidium punctatum</i> LATREILLE, 1809	LC		3				2010-2011	2007-2011		
<i>Anthidium septempinosum</i> LEPELETIER, 1841	DD		9				1991-2017	2017		2017
<i>Anthophora aestivalis</i> (PANZER, 1801)	LC		2				2012-2021			
<i>Anthophora bimaculata</i> (PANZER, 1798)	LC		7	2011	2006			2007-2015		
<i>Anthophora furcata</i> (PANZER, 1798)	LC		2					2011		2011
<i>Anthophora plumipes</i> (PALLAS, 1772)	LC	X	180	2009-(2022)	2017-(2022)	2005-2018	1990-2010	2007-2018		2007-2017
<i>Anthophora quadrimaculata</i> (PANZER, 1798)	DD		1				2020			
<i>Anthophora retusa</i> (LINNAEUS, 1758)	LC		15		2019-2021			2015		
<i>Apis mellifera</i> LINNAEUS, 1758	DD		1660	2008-(2022)	2002-2021	2010-2021	1991-2021	2007-(2022)		2011-(2022)
<i>Bombus campestris</i> (PANZER, 1801)	LC		1					2008		
<i>Bombus hortorum</i> (LINNAEUS, 1761)	LC	X	240	2009-2019	2017	2005-2018	1995-2017	2011-(2022)		2007-2017
<i>Bombus humilis</i> ILIGER, 1806	LC		3				1991			2011
<i>Bombus hypnorum</i> (LINNAEUS, 1758)	LC		40	2011-(2022)	2014-2020	2018	1994-2009	2012-(2022)		2011-2017

<i>Bombus lapidarius</i> (LINNAEUS, 1758)	LC	X	654	2008-2020	2002-2021	2005-2018	1991-2017	2003-2020	1995-2020
<i>Bombus lucorum</i> (LINNAEUS, 1761)	LC		124	2011	2015	2006-2018	1994	2006-2020	2011-2017
<i>Bombus muscorum</i> (LINNAEUS, 1758)	VU		3			2005-2018			
<i>Bombus pascuorum</i> (SCOPOLI, 1763)	LC	X	764	2008-(2022)	2002-2021	2005-2018	1991-2017	2006-2021	2011-(2022)
<i>Bombus pratorum</i> (LINNAEUS, 1761)	LC	X	373	2008-(2022)	2002-2021	2005-2018	1995-2017	2009-2021	2010-2020
<i>Bombus ruderarius</i> (MÜLLER, 1776)	LC		20	2009-2011		2018	2011-2017	2007-2011	2010-2011
<i>Bombus ruderatus</i> (FABRICIUS, 1775)	LC		9	2009		2018		2007-2019	2011
<i>Bombus rupestris</i> (FABRICIUS, 1793)	LC		7			2018		2011	2011
<i>Bombus sylvarum</i> (LINNAEUS, 1761)	LC		67	2008-2011	2020	2018	1991-2011	2008-2020	2011
<i>Bombus sylvestris</i> (LEPELETIER, 1833)	LC		110	2011-2021	2015-2021		2009	2012-2019	2011
<i>Bombus terrestris</i> (LINNAEUS, 1758)	LC	X	1121	2008-(2022)	2002-2020	2005-2018	1993-2017	2003-(2022)	1995-2020
<i>Bombus vestalis</i> (GEOFFROY IN FOURCROY, 1785)	LC	X	138	2011-(2022)	2014-2020	2018	1993-2021	2007-2020	1995-2017
<i>Ceratina chalybea</i> CHEVRIER, 1872	LC		2			2005			2020
<i>Ceratina cucurbitina</i> (ROSSI, 1792)	LC		5			2008	1991-2017	2008	2011
<i>Ceratina cyanea</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	LC		10		2017	2008	1991-2014	2017	2017
<i>Chelostoma campanularum</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	LC		7				1991-2014		
<i>Chelostoma distinctum</i> (STÖCKHERT, 1929)	LC		11			2008			
<i>Chelostoma florisomme</i> (LINNAEUS, 1758)	LC		6	2011-2012				2008	2011
<i>Chelostoma rapunculi</i> (LEPELETIER, 1841)	LC		14		2017		2012-2014	2010-2020	2017
<i>Coelioxys afra</i> LEPELETIER, 1841	LC		4	2020	2006	2005			
<i>Coelioxys aurolimbata</i> FÖRSTER, 1853	LC		1					2006	
<i>Coelioxys conoidea</i> (ILLIGER, 1806)	LC		2				2017	2012	
<i>Coelioxys elongata</i> LEPELETIER, 1841	LC		1			2006			
<i>Coelioxys inermis</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	LC		1					2017	
<i>Coelioxys rufescens</i> LEPELETIER & AUDINET-SERVILLE, 1825	LC		1			2006			
<i>Colletes cunicularius</i> (LINNAEUS, 1761)	LC	X	108	2007-2021		2017	2010-2017	2006-2021	2011-2017
<i>Colletes daviesanus</i> SMITH, 1846	LC		2					2017	
<i>Colletes fodiens</i> (GEOFFROY IN FOURCROY, 1785)	VU		1					2017	
<i>Colletes gallicus</i> RADOSZKOWSKI, 1891	LC		1				2010		
<i>Colletes hederæ</i> SCHMIDT & WESTRICH, 1993	LC	X	37	2010-(2022)			2015-2017	2006-2018	2014-2018
<i>Colletes hylaeiformis</i> EVERS-MANN, 1852	LC		2				2017-2021	2015	
<i>Colletes nigricans</i> GISTEL, 1857	LC		2				2010	2008	
<i>Colletes similis</i> SCHENCK, 1853	LC		3				2017	2008	
<i>Colletes succinctus</i> (LINNAEUS, 1758)	NT		1				2019		
<i>Dasygaster argentata</i> PANZER, 1809	NT		5				2009-2021		
<i>Dasygaster hirtipes</i> (FABRICIUS, 1793)	LC	X	108	2015-2020	2007	2017	2010-2017	2011-2021	2017
<i>Dasygaster morawitzi</i> RADCHENKO, 2016	nc		14				2017		2017
<i>Epeoloides coecutiens</i> (FABRICIUS, 1775)	LC		1						2011
<i>Epeolus cruciger</i> (PANZER, 1799)	NT		4				1995-2015	2007	1995
<i>Epeolus variegatus</i> (LINNAEUS, 1758)	LC		2				2015		
<i>Eucera chrysopyga</i> PÉREZ, 1880	LC		1						2017
<i>Eucera longicornis</i> (LINNAEUS, 1758)	LC		35	2014-(2022)		2005-2010	2005-2013	2005-2021	2010
<i>Eucera nigrescens</i> PÉREZ, 1880	LC		41	2008-2020			1995-2017	2007-2019	
<i>Halictus compressus</i> (WALCKENAER, 1802)	LC		4	2011					2011
<i>Halictus langobardicus</i> BLÜTHGEN, 1944	LC		70				2017	2017	2017
<i>Halictus maculatus</i> SMITH, 1848	LC		55	2011			2017	2010-2017	2017
<i>Halictus quadricinctus</i> (FABRICIUS, 1777)	NT		58				2017-2019	2017	2011-2017
<i>Halictus rubicundus</i> (CHRIST, 1791)	LC		158	2011		2006		2007-2012	2011
<i>Halictus scabiosae</i> (ROSSI, 1790)	LC	X	685	2009-(2022)		2002-2018	2017	2007-(2022)	2017-(2022)
<i>Halictus sexcinctus</i> (FABRICIUS, 1775)	LC		21	2011		2002-2007	2017	2011	2011-2017
<i>Halictus simplex</i> BLÜTHGEN, 1923	LC		14				1997-2017	2009-2010	2011
<i>Heriades truncorum</i> (LINNAEUS, 1758)	LC		13	2015			1991-2014	2009-2020	2011-2017
<i>Hoplitis adunca</i> (PANZER, 1798)	LC		24	2020			2007-2021	2007-2015	2017
<i>Hoplitis leucomelana</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	LC		8				1991-2014	2017	2017
<i>Hylaeus brevicornis</i> NYLANDER, 1852	LC		6				1990-1991		2017
<i>Hylaeus clypearis</i> (SCHENCK, 1853)	LC		1						2017
<i>Hylaeus communis</i> NYLANDER, 1852	LC		3				1995	2011	
<i>Hylaeus cornutus</i> CURTIS, 1831	LC		3	2011		2008			2011
<i>Hylaeus difformis</i> (EVERSMANN, 1852)	LC		1						2017
<i>Hylaeus dilatatus</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	LC		2						2017
<i>Hylaeus gibbus</i> SAUNDERS, 1850	LC		2						2017
<i>Hylaeus gredleri</i> FÖRSTER, 1871	LC		4				1991	2011	2017
<i>Hylaeus hyalinatus</i> SMITH, 1842	LC		9			2008	2014		2017
<i>Hylaeus nigrinus</i> (FABRICIUS, 1798)	LC		3	2020		2008			2017

<i>Hylaeus pectoralis</i> FÖRSTER, 1871	DD		1					2011	
<i>Hylaeus punctatus</i> (BRULLÉ, 1832)	LC		7						2017
<i>Hylaeus signatus</i> (PANZER, 1798)	LC		1						2017
<i>Hylaeus sinuatus</i> (SCHENCK, 1853)	LC		1				2019	2007	
<i>Hylaeus variegatus</i> (FABRICIUS, 1798)	LC		7	2020			2021	2020	2017
<i>Lasioglossum aeratum</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	LC		8	2011					2017
<i>Lasioglossum albipes</i> (FABRICIUS, 1781)	LC		32					2017	2011-2017
<i>Lasioglossum bluethgeni</i> EBMER, 1971	LC		66					2017	2011-2017
<i>Lasioglossum buccale</i> (PÉREZ, 1903)	LC		1					2017	
<i>Lasioglossum calceatum</i> (SCOPOLI, 1763)	LC		426	2008-2011			2017	2007-2019	2011-2017
<i>Lasioglossum corvinum</i> (MORAWITZ, 1877)	LC		2						2011
<i>Lasioglossum costulatum</i> (KRIECHBAUMER, 1873)	NT		22	2011					2011
<i>Lasioglossum fulvicorne</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	LC		71	2011			2014	2009	2011
<i>Lasioglossum glabriusculum</i> (MORAWITZ, 1872)	LC		11	2011				2007-2017	2011
<i>Lasioglossum griseolum</i> (MORAWITZ, 1872)	DD		6				2017	2007-2017	
<i>Lasioglossum intermedium</i> (SCHENCK, 1869)	NT		2					2017	2011
<i>Lasioglossum interruptum</i> (PANZER, 1798)	LC		42	2011				2011-2012	2011
<i>Lasioglossum laevigatum</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	NT		23				2010		2011
<i>Lasioglossum laticeps</i> (SCHENCK, 1869)	LC		247	2011			1995-2017	2007-2017	2011-2017
<i>Lasioglossum lativentre</i> (SCHENCK, 1853)	LC		76	2011				2007-2017	2011-2017
<i>Lasioglossum leucopus</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	LC		6	2011					2011
<i>Lasioglossum leucozonium</i> (SCHRANK, 1781)	LC		244	2011			2010-2017	2007-2017	2011-2017
<i>Lasioglossum limbellum</i> (MORAWITZ, 1876)	DD		2						2017
<i>Lasioglossum lineare</i> (SCHENCK, 1869)	DD		64					2007	2011
<i>Lasioglossum majus</i> (NYLANDER, 1852)	NT		54	2011				2017	2011
<i>Lasioglossum malachurum</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	LC		702	2011		2006	1991-2017	2007-2019	2011-2017
<i>Lasioglossum marginatum</i> (BRULLÉ, 1832)	LC		54				2017	2007-2017	2011
<i>Lasioglossum medinai</i> (VACHAL, 1895)	nc		3					2017	2017
<i>Lasioglossum mediterraneum</i> (BLÜTHGEN, 1926)	LC		2						2017
<i>Lasioglossum minutissimum</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	LC		120	2011			1991-2014	2007-2017	2011-2017
<i>Lasioglossum monstrificum</i> (MORAWITZ, 1891)	NT		19						2011-2017
<i>Lasioglossum morio</i> (FABRICIUS, 1793)	LC		586	2011			1990-2017	2007-2017	2011-2017
<i>Lasioglossum nitidiusculum</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	LC		2	2011					2011
<i>Lasioglossum nitidulum</i> (FABRICIUS, 1804)	LC		48				2017	2017	2017
<i>Lasioglossum pallens</i> (BRULLÉ, 1832)	LC		116	2011			1991-2017	2011-2017	2011
<i>Lasioglossum parvulum</i> (SCHENCK, 1853)	LC		3	2011					2011
<i>Lasioglossum pauperatum</i> (BRULLÉ, 1832)	LC		180	2011			1991	2007-2017	2011-2017
<i>Lasioglossum pauxillum</i> (SCHENCK, 1853)	LC		434				2017	2011-2017	2011-2017
<i>Lasioglossum politum</i> (SCHENCK, 1853)	LC		60	2011			1991-2017		2011
<i>Lasioglossum prasinum</i> (SMITH, 1848)	NT		1						2011
<i>Lasioglossum punctatissimum</i> (SCHENCK, 1853)	LC		22	2011			1991-2014	2007	2011-2017
<i>Lasioglossum puncticolle</i> (MORAWITZ, 1872)	LC		22	2011			1991	2007-2017	2011
<i>Lasioglossum pygmaeum</i> (SCHENCK, 1853)	NT		17	2011				2017	2011
<i>Lasioglossum quadrinotatum</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	NT		4				2009		2007-2011
<i>Lasioglossum semilucens</i> (ALFKEN, 1914)	LC		1	2011					
<i>Lasioglossum sexnotatum</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	NT		47	2011			2014	2017	2011-2017
<i>Lasioglossum subhirtum</i> (LEPELETIER, 1841)	LC		119	2011				2007-2017	2011
<i>Lasioglossum villosulum</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	LC		131	2011			1991-2017	2007-2017	2011-2017
<i>Lasioglossum xanthopus</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	NT		64	2011				2007-2017	2011
<i>Lasioglossum zonulum</i> (SMITH, 1848)	LC		233	2008-2011			1991-2014	2007-2017	2011-2017
<i>Lithurgus chrysurus</i> FONSCOLOMBE, 1834	LC		4	2020				2006-2020	
<i>Lithurgus cornutus</i> (FABRICIUS, 1787)	LC		7	2020			2021	2006-2014	
<i>Macropis europaea</i> WARNCKE, 1973	LC		3					2011	2011-2017
<i>Megachile centuncularis</i> (LINNAEUS, 1758)	LC		14			2006	1991-2014	2007	2017
<i>Megachile circumcincta</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	LC		2				2012-2013		
<i>Megachile ericetorum</i> LEPELETIER, 1841	LC		6	2020			1990-2009	2020	2017
<i>Megachile genalis</i> MORAWITZ, 1880	DD		1					2017	
<i>Megachile lagopoda</i> (LINNAEUS, 1761)	LC		2				2010	2012	
<i>Megachile ligniseca</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	DD		1						2017
<i>Megachile maritima</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	DD		7				2021	2014-2017	2017
<i>Megachile pilidens</i> ALFKEN, 1924	LC		6	2020				2011	2011-2017
<i>Megachile rotundata</i> (FABRICIUS, 1787)	DD		1				2009		
<i>Megachile versicolor</i> SMITH, 1844	DD		4			2006	1991-1995	2014	
<i>Megachile willughbiella</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	LC		11		2017		2014-2017	2011	2017

<i>Melecta albifrons</i> (FORSTER, 1771)	LC		12		2017			2008-2018	
<i>Melecta luctuosa</i> (SCOPOLI, 1770)	LC		1					2018	
<i>Melitta haemorrhoidalis</i> (FABRICIUS, 1775)	LC		2				2021	(2022)	
<i>Melitta leporina</i> (PANZER, 1799)	LC		5	2009				2010	2017
<i>Melitta nigricans</i> ALFKEN, 1905	LC		16			2005-208	1991-2014	2008-2011	2011-2017
<i>Melitta tricineta</i> KIRBY, 1802	NT		11	2011					
<i>Melitturga clavicornis</i> (LATREILLE, 1806)	NT		8					2008-2021	
<i>Nomada alboguttata</i> HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1839	LC		2					2019	
<i>Nomada armata</i> HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1839	NT		1					2020	
<i>Nomada bifasciata</i> OLIVIER, 1811	LC		18	2009-2020	2017		2010	2007-2019	
<i>Nomada braunsiana</i> SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1882	NT		1					2007	
<i>Nomada fabriciana</i> (LINNAEUS, 1767)	LC		22	2012	2017	2010	2008-2017	2007-2019	
<i>Nomada ferruginata</i> (LINNAEUS, 1767)	LC		2				2017		2007
<i>Nomada flava</i> PANZER, 1798	LC		10	2012-2014		2005	(1989)	2007	2008
<i>Nomada flavoguttata</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	LC		17	2012	2008		2017	2007-2010	2017
<i>Nomada fucata</i> PANZER, 1798	LC		8	2020	2017			2007-(2022)	2017
<i>Nomada goodeniana</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	LC		21	2012	2017	1997-2005	1996-2017	2007-2020	
<i>Nomada lathburiana</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	LC	X	17	2010	2008	2005-2010		2005-2020	2022
<i>Nomada marshamella</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	LC		5	2020	2017	2010	1994	2017	
<i>Nomada melathoracica</i> IMHOFF, 1834	LC		1		2005				
<i>Nomada panurgina</i> MORAWITZ, 1868	LC		1					2009	
<i>Nomada panzeri</i> LEPELETIER, 1841	LC		3					2007	
<i>Nomada pulchra</i> ARNOLD, 1888	EN		1				2011		
<i>Nomada ruficornis</i> (LINNAEUS, 1758)	LC		7					2007-2008	2017
<i>Nomada rufipes</i> FABRICIUS, 1793	LC		2			2002	2007		
<i>Nomada sexfasciata</i> PANZER, 1799	LC		6	2010			2009-2014	2016	
<i>Nomada signata</i> JURINE, 1807	LC		6	2019				2007	
<i>Nomada stigma</i> FABRICIUS, 1804	LC		1					2007	
<i>Nomada striata</i> FABRICIUS, 1793	LC		1						2017
<i>Nomada succincta</i> PANZER, 1798	LC		19	2009-2012	2017-2021		2009	2008	
<i>Nomada tridentirostris</i> DOURS, 1873	LC		1					2010	
<i>Nomada zonata</i> PANZER, 1798	LC		8				2004-2014	2008-2010	
<i>Osmia aurulenta</i> (PANZER, 1799)	LC		6				2021	2007-2012	
<i>Osmia bicolor</i> (SCHRANK, 1781)	LC		73			2010		2012-2016	2011-2016
<i>Osmia bicornis</i> (LINNAEUS, 1758)	LC	X	140	2016-2021	2016-2017		1995-2017	2007-2017	2011-2017
<i>Osmia brevicornis</i> (FABRICIUS, 1798)	LC		2					2007	
<i>Osmia caerulescens</i> (LINNAEUS, 1758)	LC		15	2020	2017		2011-2021	2016-2021	
<i>Osmia cornuta</i> (LATREILLE, 1805)	LC	X	68	2008-(2022)	2017-2018	2018	2009-2020	2006-2021	2013-2017
<i>Osmia gallarum</i> SPINOLA, 1807	LC		1					2017	
<i>Osmia leaiana</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	LC		22		2017		1991-2017	2007-2020	2017
<i>Osmia niveata</i> (FABRICIUS, 1804)	LC		2	2020				2017	
<i>Osmia rufohirta</i> LATREILLE, 1811	LC		1					2012	
<i>Osmia spinulosa</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	LC		1					2006	
<i>Panurgus calcaratus</i> (SCOPOLI, 1763)	LC		4				2017		2017
<i>Panurgus dentipes</i> LATREILLE, 1811	LC		110				2017	2007-2017	2017
<i>Pseudoanthidium nanum</i> (MOCSÁRY, 1881)	DD		1					2016	
<i>Rophites quinquespinosus</i> SPINOLA, 1807	NT		2				1995		
<i>Seladonia confusa</i> (SMITH, 1853)	LC		1						2011
<i>Seladonia subaurata</i> (ROSSI, 1792)	LC		52	2011			1996-2017	2007-2017	2011-2017
<i>Seladonia submediterranea</i> PAULY, 2015	LC		1						2017
<i>Seladonia tumulorum</i> (LINNAEUS, 1758)	LC		198	2011			2017	2007-2017	2011-2017
<i>Sphecodes albilabris</i> (FABRICIUS, 1793)	LC	X	26	2018-2021	2010-2017	2005	1990-2017	2007-2021	2007
<i>Sphecodes crassus</i> THOMSON, 1870	LC		1					2017	
<i>Sphecodes ephippius</i> (LINNAEUS, 1767)	LC		3				1991-2012		
<i>Sphecodes gibbus</i> (LINNAEUS, 1758)	LC		3			2004-2005	1991		
<i>Sphecodes majalis</i> PÉREZ, 1903	NT		1					2017	
<i>Sphecodes monilicornis</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	LC		7	2020		2004	1991	2007	
<i>Sphecodes niger</i> HAGENS, 1874	LC		3					2007-2017	
<i>Sphecodes pseudofasciatus</i> BLÜTHGEN, 1925	DD		1						2017
<i>Sphecodes puncticeps</i> THOMSON, 1870	LC		3			2004	2015		
<i>Sphecodes rubicundus</i> HAGENS, 1875	NT		1					2007	
<i>Sphecodes ruficrus</i> (ERICHSON IN WALT, 1835)	LC		4					2007-2017	
<i>Stelis annulata</i> (LEPELETIER, 1841)	DD		1				2017		
<i>Stelis breviscula</i> (NYLANDER, 1848)	LC		1				2014		

<i>Stelis odontopyga</i> NOSKIEWICZ, 1926	LC		3						2011
<i>Stelis ornatula</i> (KLUG, 1808)	LC		2				1991-1995		
<i>Stelis phaeoptera</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	DD		3		2017		1991		
<i>Stelis punctulatissima</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	LC		2					2007	2017
<i>Stelis simillima</i> MORAWITZ, 1875	LC		1					2020	
<i>Tetralonia malvae</i> (ROSSI, 1790)	LC		4	2009		2006		2009-2014	
<i>Tetraloniella dentata</i> (GERMAR, 1839)	LC		4				2005	2007-2014	2017
<i>Tetraloniella salicariae</i> (LEPELETIER, 1841)	DD		1			2005			
<i>Trachusa byssina</i> (PANZER, 1798)	LC		2					2012-2014	
<i>Trachusa interrupta</i> (FABRICIUS, 1781)	EN		6					2017	(2022)
<i>Xylocopa iris</i> (CHRIST, 1791)	LC		5					2011-2017	2019
<i>Xylocopa valga</i> GERSTÄCKER, 1872	LC		5		2021			2009-2018	2011
<i>Xylocopa violacea</i> (LINNAEUS, 1758)	LC	X	470	2009-(2022)	2015-2021	2011-2018	2012-2018	2013-(2022)	1994-2018

Tableau II. Données antérieures à 1990 relatives à la présence d'espèces d'abeilles en région Centre-Val de Loire.

CVL = région Centre-Val de Loire. 37 = département d'Indre et Loire. Les données sont dues à Klaus WARNCKE, Roch DESMIERS DE CHENON et Jean LECLERCQ, l'essentiel étant présent dans l'atlas de WARNCKE *et al.* (1974).

Espèces concernées	Date	Présence géographique*
<i>Andrena haemorrhoa</i> (FABRICIUS, 1781)	< 1950	CVL
<i>Andrena marginata</i> FABRICIUS, 1777	< 1950	CVL
<i>Andrena bimaculata</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	Entre 1950 et 1974	CVL
<i>Andrena bucephala</i> STEPHENS, 1846	Entre 1950 et 1974	CVL
<i>Andrena chrysoceles</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	Entre 1950 et 1974	CVL
<i>Andrena decipiens</i> SCHENCK, 1861	Entre 1950 et 1974	CVL
<i>Andrena dorsata</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	Entre 1950 et 1974	CVL
<i>Andrena flavipes</i> PANZER, 1799	Entre 1950 et 1975	CVL
<i>Andrena florea</i> FABRICIUS, 1793	Entre 1950 et 1974	CVL
<i>Andrena fucata</i> SMITH, 1847	Entre 1950 et 1974	CVL
<i>Andrena fulva</i> (MÜLLER, 1766)	Entre 1950 et 1974	CVL
<i>Andrena haemorrhoa</i> (FABRICIUS, 1781)	Entre 1950 et 1974	CVL
<i>Andrena hattorfiana</i> (FABRICIUS, 1775)	Entre 1950 et 1974	CVL
<i>Andrena helvola</i> (LINNAEUS, 1758)	Entre 1950 et 1974	CVL
<i>Andrena lathyri</i> ALFKEN, 1898	Entre 1950 et 1974	CVL
<i>Andrena minutula</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	Entre 1950 et 1974	CVL
<i>Andrena nigroaenea</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	Entre 1950 et 1974	CVL
<i>Andrena nitida</i> (MÜLLER, 1776)	Entre 1950 et 1974	CVL
<i>Andrena niduscula</i> SCHENCK, 1853	Entre 1950 et 1974	CVL
<i>Andrena niveata</i> FRIESE, 1887	Entre 1950 et 1974	CVL
<i>Andrena ovatula</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	Entre 1950 et 1974	CVL
<i>Andrena pandellei</i> PÉREZ, 1895	Entre 1950 et 1974	CVL
<i>Andrena pilipes</i> FABRICIUS, 1781	Entre 1950 et 1974	CVL
<i>Andrena praecox</i> (SCOPELLI, 1763)	Entre 1950 et 1974	CVL
<i>Andrena ranunculi</i> SCHMIEDEKNECHT, 1884	Entre 1950 et 1974	CVL
<i>Andrena rosae</i> PANZER, 1801	Entre 1950 et 1974	CVL
<i>Andrena bucephala</i> STEPHENS, 1846	1974	37
<i>Andrena lathyri</i> ALFKEN, 1898	1974	37
<i>Andrena limata</i> SMITH, 1853	1974	37
<i>Andrena minutula</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	1974	37
<i>Andrena ovatula</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	1974	37
<i>Andrena trimmerana</i> (KIRBY, 1802)	1974	37
<i>Sphecodes alternatus</i> SMITH, 1853	17/08/1984	37
<i>Sphecodes gibbus</i> (LINNAEUS, 1758)	16/08/1984	37
<i>Sphecodes gibbus</i> (LINNAEUS, 1758)	22/05/1988	37

DISCUSSION

Les résultats obtenus lors de cette étude constituent une première étape dans la connaissance des pollinisateurs Apiformes de notre région, mais il sera important de l'enrichir et de la mettre à jour, en particulier sur certaines zones géographiques de la région (Indre, Eure et Loir) ainsi

chez la famille des Apidae. Plusieurs pistes peuvent être envisagées pour y parvenir.

Une première piste serait de pouvoir accéder à divers spécimens et bases de données qui n'ont, à ce jour, pas pu

être pris en compte et qui sont en dehors de la sphère SINP :

- spécimens d'abeilles collectés par des naturalistes de la région mais non vérifiés par des spécialistes qui pourraient comprendre, d'après une estimation sommaire, une quarantaine d'espèces supplémentaires absentes de la présente liste.
- spécimens issus de piégeage ou de collecte d'hyménoptères non exploités à ce jour (provenant d'études réalisées, en particulier, en milieu agricole par la Chambre d'agriculture, de données muséales, de bases de données naturalistes existantes dans les départements de la Région (comme Obs'28, Obs'Indre, Obs'37, Obs'45, Obs'41).

Les identifications et confirmations nécessaires, selon les

traits morphologiques ou par analyse génétique, devraient être confiées à des experts du domaine des Apoïdes Apiformes.

Une deuxième piste pourrait être d'encourager et d'inciter, à travers des financements *ad hoc*, les associations et organismes disposant des compétences nécessaires, à engager des campagnes de prospection sur ces groupes d'espèces, en particulier dans les départements les moins renseignés à ce jour.

Ces deux pistes pourraient ainsi permettre de produire, à l'horizon de cinq à dix ans, une liste révisée et enrichie des abeilles présentes en région Centre-Val de Loire.

REMERCIEMENTS

L'auteur tient à adresser ses plus vifs remerciements :

- aux auteurs de données, listées ci-après par ordre alphabétique, avec des remerciements particuliers à Carlos LOPES VAAMONDE et Irène VILLALTA (IRBI), à CERCOPE (Jean-Louis PRATZ, Sébastien DAMOISEAU et Christian SALLÉ), à Samantha BAILEY, à Serge GADOUM ainsi qu'à Violette LE FÉON pour la mise à disposition d'une grande partie de leurs données, et à Christian COCQUEMPOT pour la mise à disposition de sa compilation des données de l'Indre-et-Loire (37).

Jean-François ABGRALL, Michel AMBROISE, William ARIAL et collaborateurs, Samantha BAILEY, Jean-Philippe BARBARIN, Jean-Pierre BARBAT, Jean-Christophe BARTOLUCCI, Mathilde BAUDE, Jacqueline BEAUMONT, Kévin BILLARD, Michel BINON, Jérôme BLANC et collaborateurs, Thierry BLANCHARD, Sylvie BOUCHER, Philippe BOURLET, Micheline & Jacques BOURREAU, Fabien BRUNET, Dominique CADORET-HOUY, Alain CALLET, Alain CASSANT, Sylvie CAUX, Colette & Thierry CENSE, Jean-Louis Charleux, Solène CHARTIER, Caryle CHARTON, Adrien CHOREIN, Michel CHOVET, Valentin CIAMARONE, Christian COCQUEMPOT, ? CONSTANT, Maxime CORNILLON, Franck D'ATHIS, Sébastien DAMOISEAU, Bernard DEFAUT, Damien DEFLANDRE, Jan DEVALEZ, Lola DIEBOLT, Loïc DODY, Romuald DOHOGNE, Emmanuel DOLLO, Pierrick DORÉ, Cassandra DOUBLET, Daniel DUFOUR, Éric DUFRÈNE, Pascal DUMESNIL, André DUTERTRE, Théo EMERIAU, Julien FLEURY, Jean-Pierre FONBAUSTIER, Robert FONFRIA, Philippe FOUILLET, Serge GADOUM, Anaïs GARNIER, David GENOUD, Michel GERVAIS, Philippe GILOT, Céline GRASSI, Jacques HAMON, Jean-Jacques HARISTOY, Valentin HECK, Martine HELLEMAN, Monique & Pierre HERVAT, Arnaud HORELLOU, Pierre HUGUENY, Maryvonne & Daniel INGREMEAU, Stéphanie ISERBYT, Xavier JAPIOT, Georges JARDIN, Frédéric JARRY, Anthonin JOURDAS, Denis KEITH, Aurélie LACOEUILHE, Anne-Marie & Jacques LAMY, Alexandre LANGLAIS, Alain LARIVIÈRE, Florian Laurenceau, Sylvie LE BERRE, Violette LE FÉON, Romain LEDET, Vincianne LEDUC, François LEFEBVRE, Patrick LEGRAND, Valérie LE MERCIER, Bernard LEMESLE, Jean-Michel LETT, Francis L'HERPINIÈRE, Tjitske LUBACH, Guillaume MARCHAIS, Jacques MARQUET, Benoît MARTHA, D. (?) MARTIN, Philippe MAUBERT, Jean MAURETTE, Marc MAZURIER, Olivier MERIOT, Adrien METIVIER, Denis MICHEZ, Carl MOLIARD, Eugène MONTOCCHIO, Marie MULLER, Pierre NOËL, Coline NOYAU, Roland PAILLAT et collaborateurs, Laurent PALUSSIÈRE, Adrien PATRIGEON, Frédéric PELLETIER, Christian PENOT, Alain PERTHUIS, Magali PETTITI, Delphine PICARD, Alain PICARD, Delphine PICART, Pierre PLAT, Alexis PONNET, Jean-Luc POTIRON, Jean-Louis PRATZ, Michel PRÉVOST, Tom RATZ, Emmanuel REGENT, Quentin REVEL, Yannick RICORDEL, Stuart P. M. ROBERTS, Anna RODRIGUEZ, Marlène ROUSSEAU, Annie SALLÉ, Christian SALLÉ, Gérard SAUVÉ, Maximilian SCHWARTZ, Philippe SOULAS, Emmanuelle SPEH, J. (?) THÉVENOT, Chloé THIERRY, Émilien TORTET, Patryck VAUCOULON, Nicolas VERECKEN, Annie VICENTE, Arneau VILLE, ? VINET, Jacques VION, Klaus WARNCKE et collaborateurs.

à travers, le cas échéant, les structures suivantes :

Apoidea Gallica, CDPNE, Conservatoire d'espaces naturels Centre-Val de Loire, CERCOPE, CPIE Touraine Val de Loire, Entomologie Tourangelle et Ligérienne, Fédération de Pêche Indre et Loire, FNE Centre-Val de Loire, Forestry Ecosystems Research Unit, Indre Nature, Ingénierie Environnement Aménagement, INPN, IRSTEA, Loiret Nature Environnement, Ministère de l'Agriculture, Nature Centre, Perche Nature, PNR Perche, POLLEN, Réserve Naturelle Nationale de Grand Pierre et Vitain, SEPANT Touraine, Société herpétologique de Touraine, Société pour le Muséum d'Orléans et les Sciences, Université François-Rabelais de Tours, Université d'Orléans.

- aux experts qui ont identifié un grand nombre des spécimens : Matthieu AUBERT, Éric DUFRÈNE, Serge GADOUM, David GENOUD, Gérard LE GOFF, Gilles MAHÉ, Maximilian SCHWARZ et Jan SMIT.
- aux relecteurs « critiques » de cette liste : Matthieu AUBERT, Éric DUFRÈNE, Serge GADOUM, David GENOUD et Gilles MAHÉ.

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68 rue du Onze Novembre
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<https://oabeilles.net/>

Sommaire • Contents

Couverture • Cover	i
B. GESLIN Éditorial : Un pas après l'autre Editorial: One step at the time	ii
T. CASSAR <i>Megachile parietina</i> (GEOFFROY, 1785), a new addition to the bee fauna of the Maltese Islands (Hymenoptera: Apoidea: Megachilidae)	1–4
M. AUBERT, M. BONIFACINO, D. GENOUD, V. LECLERCQ, B. SCHATZ First observations of <i>Eucera</i> (<i>Cubitalia</i>) <i>breviceps</i> (FRIESE, 1911) in Italy and France, with updated information on the distribution and ecology of the species (Hymenoptera: Anthophila: Apidae)	5–18
T. H. DÖRFEL New insights into the distribution of the obscure digger wasp <i>Sphex optimus</i> F. SMITH, 1856 (Hymenoptera: Apoidea: Sphecidae)	19–22
S. FLAMINIO, A. PAULY, G. CILIA, A. CORNUEL-WILLERMOZ, L. BORTOLOTTI, M. QUARANTA <i>Lasioglossum inexpectatum</i> sp. nov., a new species from Sardinia and Corsica (Hymenoptera: Apoidea: Halictidae)	23–32
L. COLINDRE Découverte de <i>Linepithema humile</i> (MAYR, 1868) sur l'île de la Réunion (France) et nouvelle mention pour l'espèce <i>Cyphomyrmex minutus</i> MAYR, 1862 avec inclusion géoréférencée des espèces rencontrées (Hymenoptera : Formicidae : Myrmicinae)	33–36
P. BOURLET Première liste des espèces d'abeilles de la région Centre-Val de Loire (France) déclinée par départements sur la période 1990-2021 (Hymenoptera : Apoidea : Anthophila)	36–46
Mentions légales • Credits	iii
Sommaire • Contents	iv

Eucera breviceps ♀
(Lozère, France, 13 June 2016)
Photo Matthieu AUBERT

